

REVIEW OPEN ACCESS

Non-Flammable Electrolytes for Safe Lithium-, Sodium-, and Potassium-Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT

The widespread deployment of rechargeable lithium-, sodium-, and potassium-ion batteries (PIBs) is critically constrained by safety concerns, particularly those associated with the flammability of conventional carbonate-based electrolytes. In response, the development of non-flammable electrolyte systems has emerged as a key strategy to mitigate thermal runaway risks and ensure the safe operation of energy storage devices. This review provided a comprehensive overview of recent advances in non-flammable electrolytes, with a focus on their chemical design, thermal stability, electrochemical performance, and compatibility with battery components. Various classes of flame-retardant materials were systematically examined, including organophosphorus compounds, halogenated solvents, ionic liquids, aqueous systems, and solid-state electrolytes. Special attention was given to the molecular mechanisms underlying flame suppression and interfacial stability, as well as strategies for balancing safety with high energy density. By summarizing state-of-the-art developments and identifying remaining challenges, including cost-effectiveness, compatibility with high-voltage electrodes, and long-term cycling stability, this review aimed to guide the rational design of intrinsically safe, high-performance battery systems for next-generation energy technologies.

1 | Introduction

With the gradual depletion of conventional fossil fuel reserves and the intensifying impact of global climate change driven by the greenhouse effect, the transition toward sustainable and environmentally friendly energy sources has become an urgent global imperative [1–5]. In this context, various forms of renewable energy [6–10], for example, solar, tidal, and wind power, have attracted widespread research interest due to their abundance, low environmental impact, and potential to reduce carbon emissions. However, despite their advantages, these energy sources are inherently constrained by external and often unpredictable natural conditions [11, 12], including meteorological variability and geographic limitations. As a result, they

exhibit significant intermittency and volatility in power output, posing considerable challenges for grid stability and large-scale integration into modern energy infrastructures [13–15].

To address these challenges, there is a growing consensus that the development of highly efficient, stable, and scalable energy storage and conversion technologies is essential [16–18]. Such systems play a pivotal role in buffering energy fluctuations, enhancing supply reliability, and enabling the flexible utilization of renewable resources. Consequently, research efforts are increasingly focused on designing novel materials [19], improving device architectures, and optimizing system-level performance to meet the rising demands of a decarbonized and resilient energy future.

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Rechargeable ion batteries have emerged as indispensable energy storage and conversion devices [20, 21], playing a pivotal role in the development and deployment of new energy technologies [22–26]. With the increasing demand for high energy density and long cycle life, battery safety has become a critical concern, particularly for large-scale and electric vehicle applications [27, 28]. In fact, a number of high-profile fire and explosion accidents involving lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have been reported worldwide in recent years, spanning electric vehicles, aviation, energy storage stations, and consumer products. To illustrate these recurring risks, representative cases are summarized in Table 1. This growing record of incidents highlights the urgency of developing safer systems. Consequently, there has been increasing interest in the design of non-flammable or flame-retardant electrolytes, which can significantly reduce fire and explosion risks associated with thermal runaway in conventional systems (Figure 1).

Since their commercialization by Sony in the early 1990s, LIBs have become the cornerstone of portable power systems. A typical LIB consists of a cathode, an anode, a separator, and an electrolyte (Figure 2A) [42–45]. Owing to their high operating voltage, low self-discharge rate, high specific energy, absence of memory effect, fast charge/discharge capability, long cycle life, and environmental friendliness, LIBs exhibit numerous advantages [46,

47]. These attributes make them ideal for compact and light-weight electronic devices such as video cameras, mobile phones, laptops, and portable measuring instruments, as well as for use as lightweight high-energy power sources in next-generation electric vehicles [48–53].

In recent years, however, the rapid increase in the cost of lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3) and cobalt [54, 55], an essential component in many cathode materials, has raised concerns about the sustainability and economic viability of LIB technology. Moreover, cobalt resources are geographically concentrated, primarily in Central Africa [56], leading to supply chain vulnerabilities. Compounding these issues is the limited lithium abundance in the Earth's crust, with an average concentration of only ~20 ppm (Figure 2B) [57]. As a result, there has been a surge of research interest in alternative rechargeable batteries based on sodium and potassium ions, which belong to the same alkali metal group as lithium.

Sodium and potassium possess significantly higher natural abundances, approximately 23,600 ppm and 15,000 ppm, respectively, making them several hundred times more plentiful than lithium in the Earth's crust [58–62]. This resource advantage offers a promising pathway toward the development of cost-effective and sustainable battery technologies.

TABLE 1 | Representative battery fire incidents in recent years.

Date	Location	Incident description	Known/suspected cause
Sep. 2025	Daejeon, South Korea	A fire at South Korea's data infrastructure center interrupted dozens of online government services including websites and email	The fire is suspected to have started with an explosion on Friday night of the battery produced by South Korea's LG energy solution
Jan. 2025	Moss Landing, USA	Fire at a large battery energy storage system; about 80% of the facility's battery modules destroyed	Exact cause under investigation; likely related to thermal runaway or system malfunction
Jan. 2025	Busan, South Korea	Fire from a portable battery in an overhead bin during taxiing; flight was aborted before take-off	Likely short circuit or overheating of a passenger's portable battery
Nov. 2024	Missouri, USA	Fire at a battery recycling/processing plant	Thermal runaway or uncontrolled reaction during battery handling/processing
Sep. 2024	Alibaba cloud data center, Singapore	Fire and explosion in the data center; part of Alibaba cloud services in the region were disrupted	Reportedly triggered by a lithium-ion battery explosion in a battery room
Feb. 2024	Ningde, China	Fire at a CATL battery factory; no casualties reported; production partially affected	Under investigation; possibly equipment fault or thermal event in battery manufacturing area
Jun. 2024	Hwaseong, South Korea	Explosion and fire at a battery factory, resulting in 23 fatalities and 8 injuries	Internal short circuit or thermal runaway triggering chain explosions; possible manufacturing or safety management issues under investigation
Feb. 2024	Toulouse region, France	Huge fire in a lithium-battery recycling plant, burning ~900 tonnes of batteries; thousands of batteries destroyed; adjacent rubber stock also caught fire	Likely ignition in stored battery stock, propagation to adjacent materials
Jul. 2023	Off coast of Netherlands	Fire aboard a car carrier vessel; one crew member died, others injured. The ship was carrying many electric vehicles	Investigators posited that a battery in one of the electric cars might have ignited, though the cause was not conclusively established

FIGURE 1 | Non-flammable electrolytes. Copyright 2022, Springer Nature. Copyright 2023, Elsevier. Copyright 2018, Springer Nature. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society. Copyright 2015, American Association for the Advancement of Science. Copyright 2014, the Electrochemical Society. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society [29–35].

Furthermore, due to their similar electrochemical behavior and comparable chemical/physical properties, sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) and potassium-ion batteries (PIBs) can operate via mechanisms analogous to those of LIBs [63–66]. In certain application scenarios, especially where volumetric energy density is not a limiting factor, for example, stationary grid-scale energy storage, SIBs and PIBs demonstrate compelling advantages due to their elemental abundance, low material costs, and environmental accessibility (Figure 2C) [67–69].

With the rapid advancement of energy storage systems [70], the issue of battery safety has garnered increasing attention from both academia and industry. It is worth noting that incidents such as the Samsung smartphone explosions in 2016 have underscored the critical importance of safety in battery applications and highlighted the inherent risks associated with conventional battery technologies [71, 72]. Among the key components of a battery, the electrolyte and electrode materials are particularly crucial, as their chemical composition directly

determines the battery's electrochemical performance and overall stability.

The selection of different electrolyte systems and electrode materials can lead to significantly divergent outcomes in terms of battery behavior, safety, and operational efficiency. In fact, many of the current challenges associated with thermal runaway, that is, a major safety concern, are rooted in the intrinsic properties of these materials [73, 74]. For example, the electrolytes employed in most commercial LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs are based on carbonate solvents, which are highly flammable. This flammability introduces serious safety hazards, especially under conditions such as overcharging, mechanical impact, or internal short circuits [75–77].

Given these pressing concerns, there is an urgent need to explore and develop next-generation battery technologies with enhanced safety profiles [78]. This includes the pursuit of novel, non-flammable electrolytes and thermally robust electrode materials, as well as innovative cell designs that can effectively

FIGURE 2 | (A) Diagram illustrating the structure of an LIB. Copyright 2004, American Chemical Society [36]. (B) Distribution of elements in the Earth's crust. Copyright 2014, American Chemical Society [37]. (C) Concept of a smart grid system. Copyright 2017, Elsevier [38]. (D) The three phases involved in battery thermal runaway. Copyright 2019, Frontiers Media S. A. [39]. (E) Fire and explosion incidents related to LIBs. Copyright 2017, Elsevier [40]. (F) Diagram showing the combustion process of battery electrolyte [41]. (G) Time progression of flame height during electrolyte combustion. Copyright 2025, Elsevier [41].

mitigate or prevent thermal runaway [79]. Addressing these challenges is essential for ensuring the safe widespread deployment of batteries in applications ranging from consumer electronics to large-scale energy storage systems.

The thermal runaway process in secondary batteries involves three distinct stages (Figure 2D) [39]: (i) Overheating stage: Under conditions such as overcharging, internal short circuits can occur, which represent one of the most critical and unpredictable triggers of thermal runaway [80]. In addition to overcharging, prolonged exposure to high ambient temperatures or electrical malfunctions can also lead to excessive internal heat accumulation within the battery, thereby increasing the risk of instability. (ii) Heat accumulation and gas release stage: As the internal temperature continues to rise, heat begins to build up and initiates a series of exothermic side reactions [81]. These reactions include the decomposition of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) on the anode, and the highly reactive interactions between the electrodes and the electrolyte. These processes generate both heat and flammable gases [82]. Once

the temperature surpasses approximately 130°C, common polymer separators such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) may begin to shrink or melt, severely compromising the physical barrier between electrodes and significantly increasing the likelihood of internal short circuits. (iii) Combustion and explosion stage: The accumulation of heat and combustible gases during the previous stages creates favorable conditions for the ignition of the organic electrolyte. This can result in violent combustion or even explosions, causing catastrophic failure of the battery and posing serious safety hazards [83–86].

As one of the primary triggers of battery fires and explosions, flammable organic electrolytes present significant safety challenges (Figure 2E). These challenges are primarily manifested in two critical aspects:

First, carbonate-based electrolytes exhibit poor oxidative stability at the cathode interface, especially when paired with high-voltage or high-nickel cathode materials [87, 88]. Because of

their limited resistance to oxidation, carbonate solvents are prone to irreversible oxidative decomposition under high-voltage conditions. This decomposition can generate gaseous byproducts such as O₂ and CO, leading to cell swelling, alterations in the electrode–electrolyte interface, and increased polarization, all of which compound the risk of thermal instability and catastrophic failure.

Second, carbonate electrolytes are inherently flammable due to their low flash points, making them direct contributors to combustion and explosion events [89]. Conventional electrolyte systems typically consist of a lithium salt dissolved in a mixture of solvents [90]: cyclic carbonates such as ethylene carbonate (EC), which offers a high dielectric constant, and linear carbonates such as dimethyl carbonate (DMC), diethyl carbonate (DEC), and ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), valued for their low viscosity and high ionic conductivity. However, these linear carbonates have extremely low flash points, that is, 17°C for DMC, 33°C for DEC, and 23°C for EMC [41], rendering them highly susceptible to ignition under conditions of elevated temperature, overcharging, short-circuiting, or thermal shock.

To address these risks while maintaining high energy density, efforts to enhance electrolyte safety have focused on two main strategies [91]: the introduction of co-solvents with flame-retardant properties and the development of intrinsically non-flammable electrolyte systems. Linear carbonates are particularly volatile, and even before reaching high temperatures, they can evaporate to form flammable vapor clouds (Figure 2F). When mixed with air, these vapors are capable of instantaneous ignition and rapid flame propagation, resulting in intense premixed flame combustion [41]. If the evaporation rate cannot sustain the combustion rate, flame height diminishes. In contrast, carbonate systems with longer molecular chains tend to release larger quantities of vapor initially [92], supporting longer-duration flames (Figure 2G). Therefore, the development of inherently non-flammable or highly flame-retardant electrolytes is emerging as a crucial strategy for fundamentally enhancing the intrinsic safety of rechargeable batteries. In parallel, non-flammable alternatives are also being explored as viable options due to their negligible volatility and high thermal stability, whereas solid-state electrolytes offer a radical shift by eliminating liquid-phase flammability altogether.

Recent progress in battery research has led to the exploration of new electrolyte systems beyond traditional organic carbonate-based formulations. Among these, ionic liquids (ILs) [77], aqueous electrolytes [93], and solid-state electrolytes (SSEs) have emerged as promising alternatives with distinct advantages in safety [94], electrochemical performance, and environmental compatibility. ILs offer wide electrochemical windows and negligible volatility, making them inherently non-flammable; this arises from their bulky and highly polar cations that resist volatilization and free-radical combustion, together with fluorinated or weakly coordinating anions that enhance thermal stability and suppress oxidative chain reactions. Aqueous electrolytes, on the other hand, provide high ionic conductivity and intrinsic fire resistance while also benefiting from low cost and environmental benignity. SSEs eliminate liquid-phase flammability altogether and enable improved mechanical stability and integration with flexible or thin-film devices. These advanced

systems, although still facing certain technical challenges, are gradually reshaping the landscape of safe and high-performance energy storage technologies.

This review systematically summarizes recent advances in the development of non-flammable electrolytes for secondary ion batteries. It begins with an overview of the thermal stability and safety limitations associated with conventional carbonate-based electrolytes, including an in-depth analysis of their decomposition mechanisms and the key factors contributing to thermal runaway in batteries. Particular attention is given to the flammability issues that arise from these traditional systems under high-voltage and high-temperature conditions. The core of this review focuses on several categories of non-flammable electrolyte systems that have emerged in recent years, including fluorinated electrolytes, phosphate-based solvents, and flame-retardant electrolyte additives. These systems are evaluated and compared in terms of their molecular structures, thermal stability, electrochemical performance, and their effectiveness in enhancing overall battery safety. In addition, ILs and aqueous electrolytes are discussed as intrinsically non-flammable systems that provide promising alternative design pathways, whereas SSEs are introduced as a fundamentally different approach with potential to eliminate flammability risks altogether.

Furthermore, this review explores current strategies for improving electrolyte safety through formulation optimization, molecular design of solvents, and the incorporation of flame-retardant additives. Emphasis is placed on how these approaches can be leveraged to strike a balance between high energy density and thermal stability, especially in the context of next-generation battery chemistries. The potential applications of non-flammable electrolytes, including ILs, aqueous systems, and SSEs, in high energy density batteries and large-scale energy storage systems are also discussed, highlighting their role in enabling safer, more reliable power solutions for both consumer electronics and grid-level storage. Finally, the review offers a forward-looking perspective on the future development of non-flammable electrolytes, identifying the critical challenges that remain, for example, maintaining long cycle life, ensuring compatibility with high-voltage electrodes, and achieving cost-effectiveness, and proposing possible directions for research and development. The insights presented aim to support the design of intrinsically safe and sustainable energy storage technologies.

2 | Impact of Existing Electrolyte Systems on Battery Safety

The electrolyte is critical for rechargeable batteries, serving as the medium for ion transport between the cathode and anode [95]. It functions as the conductive bridge that links the two electrodes, enabling electrochemical reactions and current flow. Beyond its basic role, the choice of electrolyte significantly influences the battery's operating mechanism and directly affects key performance indicators [96], for example, specific energy, safety, cycling stability, rate capability, shelf life, and overall cost.

For LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs, the electrolyte must meet a number of fundamental requirements: (i) Chemical stability [97]: The electrolyte should be inert and non-reactive with other internal battery components, including separators, electrodes, current collectors, and packaging materials. (ii) High ionic conductivity [98]: Efficient ion transport is essential to minimize internal resistance, enhance rate performance, and maintain stable operation under high-power conditions. (iii) Thermal stability [99]: The electrolyte must remain stable over a broad temperature range without undergoing thermal decomposition. This ensures safe battery operation in both high-temperature and low-temperature environments. (iv) Wide electrochemical window [100]: To accommodate high-voltage cathode materials, the electrolyte must resist oxidation or reduction across a wide voltage range, thereby preventing electrochemical degradation. (v) Electrochemical durability [101]: The electrolyte must retain its chemical and structural integrity during repeated charge/discharge cycles, ensuring long-term performance without deterioration.

Currently, LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs predominantly employ carbonate-based organic electrolytes [102], similar to those used in LIB systems. However, these carbonate solvents are inherently flammable, posing significant safety risks under conditions such as overcharging, short-circuiting, or mechanical abuse. To address these safety concerns, several strategies have been proposed, including the development of non-flammable liquid organic electrolytes, SSEs, and gel polymer electrolytes. Among these, non-flammable liquid electrolytes may offer the most practical and economically viable path forward [103]. They retain the processability and performance advantages of conventional liquid electrolytes while significantly enhancing battery safety, making them a promising solution for next-generation energy storage technologies.

2.1 | Electrolyte-Related Thermal Runaway in Batteries

Thermal runaway is a critical safety concern in LIBs [104], referring to a self-amplifying process wherein internal heat generation surpasses the battery's capacity to dissipate heat under abusive conditions such as overcharging, internal short-circuiting, or exposure to elevated ambient temperatures [105]. Under such conditions, the rate of internal heat production becomes substantially greater than the rate of heat dissipation, leading to a rapid accumulation of thermal energy. This accumulated heat raises the internal temperature of the battery and initiates a series of highly exothermic side reactions, generating additional heat. This feedback loop can quickly spiral out of control, resulting in thermal runaway, a catastrophic failure mode characterized by fire, explosion, or venting of toxic gases (Figure 3A) [85].

The onset and progression of thermal runaway are primarily driven by a combination of thermal and chemical processes [109]. A primary contributor is internal short-circuiting, while additional factors include the decomposition of the SEI on the

anode, thermal breakdown of the liquid electrolyte, and exothermic reactions between the electrolyte and both cathode and anode materials. In more severe cases, the flammable electrolyte itself may ignite, further exacerbating the thermal instability [110]. These mechanisms are described in greater detail below:

- i. Internal short circuits typically arise from the penetration of lithium dendrites through the separator, mechanical damage, or thermal shrinkage of the separator, or the presence of metallic impurities that create localized conductive pathways. In these cases, the electronic insulation between the anode and cathode is partially or completely lost, allowing uncontrolled electron flow across the battery. Depending on severity, this can manifest as a soft short circuit, which gradually accelerates self-discharge and heat generation, or as a hard short circuit, which induces rapid Joule heating and potential thermal runaway. Once local temperatures exceed the stability limits of the separator and electrolyte, exothermic reactions are triggered, leading to gas evolution, pressure build-up, and in extreme cases, fire or explosion.
- ii. Decomposition of the SEI on the anode [111]. The SEI layer is a passivation layer that forms on the surface of the anode during the initial charging cycles of a LIB. It plays a crucial role in protecting the anode by preventing further direct contact between the electrolyte and the electrode material. The SEI is primarily composed of inorganic salts, alkyl carbonates, and polymeric species. However, this layer is thermally unstable. When the temperature rises, components such as alkyl carbonates may become unstable and decompose, leading to the formation of secondary reaction products (Figure 3B) [106]. These reactions can disrupt the protective nature of the SEI and generate additional heat, further accelerating the onset of thermal runaway.
- iii. Thermal decomposition of the electrolyte [112]. Lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6), the most commonly used lithium salt in commercial electrolytes, exhibits poor thermal stability. Upon exposure to elevated temperatures, it readily decomposes to produce highly reactive species such as phosphorus pentafluoride (PF_5) [113]. PF_5 can then initiate decomposition of solvent molecules, leading to a cascade of exothermic reactions that compromise the thermal stability of the electrolyte system.
- iv. Reactions between the electrolyte and the cathode [114]. At elevated temperatures, charged-state cathode materials such as lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO_2) and lithium nickel oxide (LiNiO_2) can undergo oxygen release reactions [115]. The liberated oxygen is highly reactive and may oxidize organic electrolyte solvents, generating additional heat and possibly flammable gases, thereby exacerbating the risk of thermal runaway.
- v. Reactions between the electrolyte and the anode [74]. On the anode side, materials rich in lithium and with high reductive activity can reduce electrolyte solvents into

FIGURE 3 | (A) Diagrammatic representation of the thermal runaway process in LIBs. Copyright 2025, Wiley-VCH GmbH [85]. (B) Representative images showing the stages of SEI formation. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society [106]. (C) Strategies for designing electrolytes to enhance the safety of LIBs. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society [107]. (D) Illustrations showing (top) how fire spreads and (bottom) how flame-retardant methods work to counteract it. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society [108].

hydrocarbon gases and Li₂CO₃. These reactions are not only exothermic but also contribute to gas generation within the cell, increasing internal pressure and elevating the risk of rupture or explosion.

- vi. Combustion of the electrolyte [116]. Electrolyte combustion requires three critical components: a flammable substance, an ignition source (heat), and an oxidizing agent. The combustion mechanism is complex and typically involves a network of free radical reactions, including highly reactive species such as H·, HO·, and O·. These reactions produce carbon dioxide (CO₂), water, and various carbonaceous byproducts [108]. Once ignition occurs, combustion can be self-sustaining and extremely difficult to control.

Although various protective strategies have been developed to enhance battery safety, for example, thermal shutdown separators [117], current interrupters [118], and fire-retardant additives [119], the most fundamental and effective approach lies in optimizing both the electrode materials and the electrolyte formulation. Using thermally stable cathode and anode

materials, along with safer, less flammable electrolytes, can significantly reduce the risk of thermal runaway (Figure 3D). Nevertheless, under extreme abuse conditions, if all protective mechanisms fail, the battery may still enter thermal runaway, potentially resulting in fire or explosion. Therefore, improving the thermal and chemical stability of electrode materials and reducing the flammability of electrolytes remain key areas for advancing the safety of batteries.

2.2 | Influence of Carbonate-Based Organic Electrolyte Solvents on Battery Safety

In LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs, the factors governing solvent selection are largely consistent across systems. An ideal electrolyte solvent must meet several stringent criteria to ensure both high performance and safety. These criteria include the following:

- i. Chemical inertness and electrochemical stability [120]: The solvent must be chemically inert toward both the anode and

cathode materials, avoiding side reactions during charge/discharge cycles. It should also exhibit a wide electrochemical stability window to withstand the high voltages typical in battery operation without decomposing.

- ii. Dielectric constant and viscosity properties [121]: A high dielectric constant is essential to effectively dissolve lithium/sodium/potassium salts, thereby ensuring sufficient ionic dissociation. Simultaneously, the solvent should have low viscosity to promote high ionic conductivity and efficient ion transport within the cell.
- iii. Wide liquid-phase temperature range [122]: The solvent should possess a high boiling point and low melting point to remain in the liquid phase over a broad temperature range, ensuring stable battery operation under various environmental and thermal conditions.
- iv. Good interfacial compatibility [123]: Compatibility with electrode materials is critical to promoting interfacial stability. An appropriate solvent should facilitate the formation of a robust and stable SEI or cathode electrolyte interphase (CEI), thereby enhancing the electrochemical performance and cycle life of the battery.
- v. Cycle performance and cost considerations [124]: Beyond technical performance, the solvent should contribute to high coulombic efficiency and long cycle life while also being cost-effective and readily scalable for commercial applications.

Commonly used carbonate-based solvents in LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs include both cyclic and linear carbonates, for example, ethylene carbonate (EC), propylene carbonate (PC), diethyl carbonate (DEC), dimethyl carbonate (DMC), ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), and diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (DG). The relevant physicochemical properties of these solvents are summarized in Table 2. It is worth noting that potassium metal exhibits particularly high reactivity with carbonate-based electrolytes, often resulting in lower coulombic efficiency in PIBs. This heightened reactivity poses challenges to both the safety and efficiency of PIB systems and necessitates careful formulation of compatible electrolytes.

TABLE 2 | Basic properties of common electrolyte solvents.

Solvent	Mol. Wt. (g mol ⁻¹)	ϵ	η (cP)	M.P. (°C)	B.P. (°C)	DN AN (kcal mol ⁻¹)
EC	88.06	89.6	0.1825	36.4	238.0	16.4
						11.0
PC	103.09	66.1	2.513	-49	242	15.1
						18.0
DEC	118.1	2.82	0.748	-74.3	126.8	16.0
						2-3
DMC	90.08	3.11	0.5805	4.6	90	17.2
						3
EMC	104.10	2.40	0.65	-55	108	16.0
						3
DG	134.78	7.23	1.06	-64	163	7
						10

2.3 | Influence of Electrolyte Salts on Battery Safety

In LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs, the choice of electrolyte salt plays a pivotal role in determining the overall electrochemical performance of the system. Key performance indicators influenced by the electrolyte salt include ionic conductivity [125], interfacial stability with electrodes [126], electrochemical stability window [127], and thermal and chemical safety [128]. Among the various characteristics of electrolyte salts, the nature and structure of the anion are especially influential. The anion largely governs the salt's solubility in organic solvents, its electrochemical and thermal stability, as well as its compatibility with current collectors and electrode materials [129]. Anions also affect the formation and properties of interphase layers such as the SEI and the CEI, which are crucial for long-term stability and safe operation of the battery.

Currently, the most commonly used anions in commercial and research-grade electrolyte salts include perchlorate (ClO₄⁻), hexafluorophosphate (PF₆⁻), bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (FSI⁻), and bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (TFSI⁻). Each of these anions exhibits distinct physicochemical characteristics that significantly influence the electrolyte's performance and safety profile. For instance: (i) PF₆⁻ is widely used due to its good balance of solubility and ionic conductivity, but it suffers from thermal instability and can release toxic or corrosive byproducts (e.g., HF) at elevated temperatures [130]; (ii) TFSI⁻ and FSI⁻ offer enhanced thermal and electrochemical stability and are particularly valued in high-voltage or high-temperature systems [131], although their corrosivity to certain metal current collectors requires careful formulation; and (iii) ClO₄⁻, while offering high ionic conductivity, raises safety concerns due to its strong oxidizing nature and potential explosiveness under certain conditions [132].

The selection of an appropriate anion, therefore, involves trade-offs between conductivity, stability, safety, and material compatibility [133]. The physical and chemical parameters of these commonly used anions, for example, thermal stability, oxidative potential, and ionic conductivity, have a profound

impact on battery safety and performance. A comparative overview of these properties is presented in Table 3.

Taking FSI⁻ as a representative example, this anion features a relatively small molecular structure and high ionic mobility, which contributes to the superior ionic conductivity of electrolytes formulated with it. Electrolytes based on FSI⁻ are thus particularly attractive for applications requiring fast ion transport and high-rate performance. However, one notable drawback is its tendency to induce corrosive reactions with aluminum current collectors at elevated voltages (around 4 V), thereby limiting its applicability in systems utilizing high-voltage cathode materials [134].

In contrast, TFSI⁻ exhibits enhanced suitability for high-voltage environments. This is primarily due to its larger steric bulk, symmetrical molecular geometry, and superior thermal stability [135]. These features provide it with greater oxidative resistance and compatibility with high-voltage cathodes. Although TFSI⁻-based electrolytes typically exhibit slightly lower ionic conductivity compared to their FSI⁻ counterparts, their overall electrochemical and thermal robustness makes them more advantageous in high energy density applications.

PF₆⁻ (hexafluorophosphate), the most widely adopted anion in commercial LIBs, offers a well-balanced set of properties, including good solubility, moderate conductivity, and acceptable compatibility with both electrodes and separators [136]. Nevertheless, its thermal instability remains a concern. At elevated temperatures, PF₆⁻ can undergo decomposition to produce hydrofluoric acid (HF), a highly corrosive byproduct that can degrade the SEI and significantly shorten battery lifespan while also raising safety concerns.

ClO₄⁻, although possessing a high oxidative stability and excellent ionic conductivity, is inherently a strong oxidizing agent and poses considerable explosion risk under thermal or mechanical stress [137]. These safety hazards have severely limited its industrial adoption, despite its promising electrochemical properties.

Compared with LIB systems, research on SIBs began relatively late. However, in recent years, SIBs have garnered significant attention due to the abundance of sodium resources and their inherently low cost [138]. Although sodium salts share some chemical similarities with their lithium counterparts, they also exhibit marked differences that influence electrolyte design and battery performance. For instance, sodium salts generally

possess higher melting points and flash points than analogous lithium salts, indicating superior thermodynamic stability [139]. This property is advantageous for enhancing the thermal safety of SIBs. However, sodium salts often show distinct differences in solubility, interfacial stability, and electrolyte viscosity, making the selection of an appropriate sodium salt a critical challenge in electrolyte formulation for SIBs.

Currently, the most commonly investigated sodium salts include NaPF₆, NaClO₄, NaTFSI, and NaFSI. These salts differ significantly in terms of thermal stability, ionic conductivity, and compatibility with current collectors. Previous reports reveal the thermal stabilities of these sodium salts [131, 140]. The results revealed that NaClO₄ exhibited the highest thermal decomposition temperature, indicating the best thermal stability, followed by NaTFSI and NaPF₆, with NaFSI showing the least stability. Because of its favorable overall performance and relatively low cost, NaClO₄ has emerged as one of the most widely used sodium salts in current SIB research [141]. Nevertheless, NaClO₄ has critical drawbacks. It is extremely hygroscopic and difficult to dry once exposed to moisture. Even after vacuum drying at 80°C, its residual water content can remain as high as 40 ppm, compared to less than 10 ppm for NaPF₆. Moreover, its strong oxidizing nature introduces potential safety hazards, that is, under abuse conditions such as overheating or internal short circuit, NaClO₄ can trigger thermal runaway or even explosions [142].

Although NaTFSI and NaFSI demonstrate excellent electrochemical and thermal stability, their high cost and the risk of aluminum current collector corrosion at elevated voltages limit their commercial viability [143]. In contrast, NaPF₆ offers a more balanced performance profile, with high ionic conductivity, low viscosity in carbonate-based electrolytes, and good electrochemical stability across a broad voltage window. As a result, NaPF₆ is widely regarded as one of the most promising electrolyte salts for the next generation of SIBs.

In the case of PIBs, the larger ionic radius of the potassium ion and its weaker solvation effect make the choice of electrolyte salt even more critical in influencing ion transport efficiency and interfacial stability [144]. The diminished solvation strength of potassium-ion not only facilitates higher ionic mobility but also imposes challenges in ensuring stable electrode-electrolyte interfaces.

Among the potassium salts that have received the most research attention are KPF₆, KClO₄, KTFSI, and potassium bis (fluorosulfonyl)imide (KFSI) [145]. Electrolyte systems based on these salts are generally characterized by lower viscosity and higher transference numbers, which are advantageous for enhancing the rate capability and power performance of PIBs. However, the thermal stability, safety, and compatibility of potassium salts with both anode and cathode materials remain areas requiring comprehensive evaluation. In particular, high-voltage applications and long-term cycling stability demand further investigation into potential decomposition pathways, side reactions, and current collector corrosion. As the PIB technology progresses toward practical deployment, systematic optimization of potassium salt formulations will be essential to fully leverage the cost-effectiveness and electrochemical potential of PIB systems.

TABLE 3 | Physicochemical properties of common electrolyte salt anions.

Anion	Mol. Wt. (g mol ⁻¹)	M.P. (°C)	Thermal stability	Ionic conductivity
ClO ₄ ⁻	122.4	468	Moderate	High
PF ₆ ⁻	167.9	300	Limited	Moderate
FSI ⁻	203.3	118	Good	High
TFSI ⁻	303.1	257	Excellent	Moderate to high

The selection of electrolyte salts for LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs must strike a careful balance among multiple factors, including ionic conductivity, electrochemical stability, thermal stability, safety, and cost-effectiveness. Among the available options, salts based on the PF_6^- anion remain the most widely used due to their well-balanced overall performance across diverse battery chemistries. Meanwhile, emerging anions such as TFSI^- and FSI^- have attracted increasing interest in recent years owing to their high ionic conductivity, enhanced thermal and electrochemical stability, and superior interfacial regulation capabilities. These advanced anions represent promising directions for the next generation of high-performance and safe electrolyte systems, offering considerable potential for improving the efficiency and durability of future battery technologies.

3 | Flame-Retardant Design of Electrolytes

3.1 | Organophosphorus-Based Flame-Retardant Solvents

Among the various strategies developed to enhance the safety of batteries, the incorporation of phosphorus-containing flame-retardants represents one of the earliest and most extensively studied approaches [146–148]. Organophosphorus flame-retardant additives can be broadly classified into phosphate esters, phosphonate esters, phosphinate esters, and phosphazene compounds. Early research has focused primarily on short-chain alkyl phosphate esters, such as trimethyl phosphate (TMP), triethyl phosphate (TEP), and dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP). These compounds are attractive due to their low toxicity, low cost, and excellent flame-retardant performance [149–151].

Taking TMP as an example, the flame-retardant mechanism is based on radical scavenging reactions [152]. Upon heating, TMP first vaporizes. In the gas phase, it decomposes to release phosphorus-centered radicals ($\text{P}\cdot$), which actively scavenge hydrogen radicals ($\text{H}\cdot$) in the flame, thereby interrupting the chain reactions of combustion and suppressing fire or explosion propagation. Despite these advantages, such solvents also exhibit significant drawbacks. For instance, similar to PC, TMP undergoes reductive decomposition at around 1.2 V versus Li/Li^+ , which prevents the formation of a stable SEI on graphite anodes (Figure 4A) [153, 156]. This leads to co-intercalation of solvent molecules into graphite, resulting in exfoliation and structural degradation, thereby rendering the anode electrochemically inactive. Consequently, early studies primarily used phosphate esters as additives, rather than as primary solvents.

Feng et al. [157] compared the compatibility of DMMP and diethyl ethylphosphonate (DEEP) with graphite anodes. Their findings revealed that DMMP caused severe co-intercalation and structural damage, whereas DEEP followed an irreversible reductive pathway without co-intercalation. Fortunately, Yamada and co-workers later achieved a major breakthrough by using highly concentrated lithium salt (5.3 M) in TMP-based electrolytes, enabling stable electrochemical performance (Figure 4B,C) [31]. The high concentration facilitated the formation of a robust, inorganic-rich SEI, improving compatibility

between phosphate solvents and graphite anodes. This approach has since opened new avenues for the rational design of flame-retardant electrolytes.

Building on this concept, Cao et al. [158] optimized a moderately concentrated TEP-based electrolyte (2.2 M) by adjusting the salt-to-solvent ratio, which reduced the mobility of free TEP molecules and suppressed solvent decomposition. Furthermore, by introducing fluoroethylene carbonate (FEC) and lithium bis(oxalato)borate (LiBOB) as additives, they successfully constructed a compact, hybrid inorganic–organic SEI [159], improving interfacial stability. However, high-concentration electrolytes often suffer from high cost (due to increased lithium salt content), elevated viscosity, and poor wettability with separators, posing serious challenges to their commercial viability.

To address these limitations, several structural design strategies are being explored. These include extending the alkyl chain, substituting alkyl groups with phenyl moieties, and developing cyclic phosphate structures to improve reductive stability and maintain SEI integrity, thereby enhancing compatibility with graphite anodes [160]. For example, Yamada et al. [154] developed a new flame-retardant electrolyte using a fluorinated cyclic phosphate solvent, 2-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)-1,3,2-dioxaphospholane-2-oxide (TFEP). They prepared a 0.95 M $\text{LiN}(\text{SO}_2\text{F})_2$ electrolyte in a TFEP/FEMC (1:3 v/v) solvent mixture, which led to the formation of a stable SEI layer on graphite (Figure 4D). This electrolyte enabled highly reversible cycling of graphite anodes without the need for high salt concentrations or SEI-forming additives, offering a promising non-flammable solution. Additionally, through ring-opening polymerization mechanisms (Figure 4E), a stable CEI was also formed on high-voltage cathodes, including $\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ (LNMO) and nickel-rich NMC materials (up to 4.5 V), enabling stable cycling under extreme conditions. In another study, Lai et al. [161] introduced diphenyloctyl phosphate (DPOF) into a conventional electrolyte (1 M LiPF_6 in EC:DMC:DMC = 1:1:2 w/w/w). After 50 charge/discharge cycles, they found that low concentrations (< 10%) of DPOF did not negatively impact the specific capacity of graphite cells and showed excellent compatibility with artificial graphite electrodes. Aspern et al. [155] investigated three flame retardant electrolyte additives: tris(2,2,3,3,3-pentafluoropropyl) phosphate (5F-TPrP), tris(1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoropropan-2-yl) phosphate (HFIP), and tris(1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoropropan-2-yl) phosphite (THFPP), as presented in Figure 4F,G. The results showed that when the highly fluorinated 5F-TPrP was used as a solvent at 30%, the electrolyte became completely non-flammable and had almost no adverse effect on the cycling performance of graphite/NCM111 full cells. With 1% additive, the trend was 5F-TPrP < HFIP < THFPP. 5F-TPrP and HFIP showed similar self-extinguishing time (SET) values (57.1 and 58.6 sg^{-1}), whereas THFPP (P oxidation state III) yielded a higher SET of 62.8 sg^{-1} . Thus, higher P oxidation states corresponded to lower SET values, and increasing additive content (> 5%) further reduced SET.

Phosphite esters represent another highly important class of flame-retardant additives. Representative compounds include trimethyl phosphite (TMP(i)) [162], triphenyl phosphite [TPP(i)] [163], triethyl phosphite [TEP(i)] [75, 164–166], tributyl

FIGURE 4 | (A) Cyclic voltammogram recorded for a graphite electrode using an electrolyte based on TMP. Copyright 2001, the Electrochemical Society [153]. (B) Illustration showing how cations (depicted as red spheres) intercalate into a carbon-based anode when using different electrolytes. Copyright 2018, Springer Nature [31]. (C) Comparative schematic of the formation of passivation layers: one formed from EC solvent in a standard dilute electrolyte, and the other from NaFSA salt in a highly concentrated electrolyte. Copyright 2018, Springer Nature [31]. (D) Schematic representation of the protective passivation layer that forms on the surface of graphite. Copyright 2020, Springer Nature [154]. (E) Illustration depicting the ring-opening polymerization of TFEP, which contributes to the formation of a cathode passivation layer. Copyright 2018, Springer Nature [154]. (F) Schematic diagram illustrating the functions of three electrolyte additives. (G) Measured self-extinguishing durations for electrolytes containing various compounds. Copyright 2017, Elsevier [155].

phosphite [TBP(i)] [167], tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) phosphite [TTFP(i)] [168], and tris(1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoropropan-2-yl) phosphite [THFPP(i)] [155]. Compared to phosphite compounds, phosphate esters exhibit greater thermal and chemical stability, primarily due to the lower reactivity of the P-O single bond relative to the P=O double bond present in phosphate esters. This inherent stability also translates into improved interfacial compatibility with battery electrodes. Moreover, phosphite esters contribute to the formation of stable and protective SEI layers on anodes. They can scavenge reactive species such as PF₅, thereby stabilizing LiPF₆ salts and reducing the formation of harmful byproducts. Additionally, these compounds are effective at neutralizing residual HF in the electrolyte, further enhancing the longevity and safety of the battery.

Lu et al. [162] conducted a comparative study between TMP and TMP(i) as flame-retardant additives. In flammability tests (Figure 5A), the control electrolyte (1 M LiPF₆ in EC:DEC) burned for ~45 s, whereas with 10 wt% additive the burning time was reduced to ~18 s for TMP(a) and ~25 s for TMP(i), indicating a stronger flame-retardant effect of TMP. They also found that TMP(i) not only improved the thermal stability of the electrolyte but also imposed minimal adverse effects on the electrochemical performance, making it a more favorable flame-retardant candidate for practical use. In another study, Wang et al. [169] employed fluorinated phosphite TTFP(i) in carbonate-based electrolytes for high-energy lithium-sulfur batteries. When the TTFP(i) concentration exceeded 10%, the electrolyte became flame-retardant or even non-flammable

FIGURE 5 | (A) Burning test of electrolytes containing TMP and TMP(i). Copyright 2005, Elsevier [162]. (B) Results of flame tests showing the impact of incorporating TTFP. Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH GmbH [169]. (C) Photographs of the flammability test. Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH. (D) SET tests. Copyright 2004, Elsevier [170]. (E, G) Galvanostatic charge–discharge voltage profiles and (F, H) cycling performance HFPN-containing electrolyte (E, F), TMP-containing electrolyte (G, H). Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society [171]. (I–L) SEM images of collected (I, J) TraCa, and (K, L) FPCEa samples after thermal runaway. Copyright 2025, Wiley-VCH GmbH [172].

(Figure 5B). Remarkably, the batteries also demonstrated superior electrochemical performance. At a high rate of 10 C, the lithium-sulfur cells retained almost their full capacity over 750 cycles, with a specific capacity as high as 800 mAh g^{-1} . These findings underscore the potential of phosphite-based flame-retardants, not only in suppressing flammability but also in enhancing electrochemical performance, particularly for next-generation high-energy battery chemistries.

Phosphazene-based flame-retardant compounds also represent a highly promising class of flame-retardant solvents [173]. These compounds encompass both low-molecular-weight cyclic phosphazenes and high-molecular-weight linear phosphazene polymers, characterized by their exceptional thermal and chemical stability. A notable advantage of phosphazene-based flame-retardants is their high efficacy at low concentrations (3%) [174]: even small additions can significantly reduce or completely eliminate the flammability of conventional carbonate-based electrolytes (Figure 5C). Furthermore, these compounds exhibit excellent compatibility with electrode materials, imposing minimal adverse impact on electrochemical performance, a key requirement for practical battery applications.

For instance, incorporating hexamethylphosphoramide (HMPA) into a baseline 1 M LiPF_6 in EC/EMC electrolyte significantly reduces flammability. When HMPA is added at concentrations of 20–25 wt.%, the electrolyte becomes flame-retardant, and at

concentrations between 25wt.% and 35 wt.%, it becomes completely non-flammable (Figure 5D) [170]. However, the incorporation of HMPA narrows the electrochemical window of the electrolyte, and at high concentrations, it further induces precipitation from the solution. Another well-studied example is hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene (HFPN), a fully fluorinated six-membered aromatic phosphazene ring compound. HFPN is well known for its extraordinary thermal resilience, chemical inertness, and non-coordinating nature, making it particularly suitable for high-safety electrolyte systems. In a functional electrolyte formulation consisting of 0.8 M LiPF_6 dissolved in EC/DEC/HCP (1:1.5:1 M ratio) [171], HFPN demonstrates outstanding flame-retardant performance while maintaining compatibility with the electrochemical system. The flammability of the three electrolytes was visually assessed with a butane blowlamp, under which they could not be ignited. The nonpolar phosphazene molecules, with weak electron-donating ability, do not coordinate with Li^+ and are therefore excluded from the primary solvation sheath. In graphite-based Li-ion batteries, they also avoid co-intercalation with Li^+ into the graphite lattice during charging, thereby preserving the anode structure and interface and enabling stable cycling with almost no capacity decay after 200 cycles (Figure 5E,F). In contrast, the TMP-containing electrolyte delivers $> 1000 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ but exhibits clear signs of solvent co-intercalation and decomposition, leading to rapid capacity fade (Figure 5G), whereas it maintain $\sim 100\%$ of its initial capacity over 200 cycles (Figure 5H). Zhang et al. [172]

reported that a phosphazene ($C_2H_5F_5N_3OP_3$)-based electrolyte (FPEele) significantly improved both the safety and electrochemical performance of NCM811|Gr pouch cells. Specifically, the thermal runaway trigger temperature increased by $41.7^\circ C$, whereas the peak temperature decreased by $205.7^\circ C$. Moreover, the cells sustained stable cycling at 4.5 V with 81.7% capacity retention after 200 cycles. The enhanced safety was attributed to a temperature-triggered polymerization of the phosphazene additive, which formed a uniform protective polymer layer on the cathode. This layer suppressed continuous exothermic chain reactions, including gas crosstalk between cathode and anode as well as side reactions at the electrode–electrolyte interfaces. Consequently, after thermal runaway, the control TraCell was almost completely burned (Figure 5I,J), whereas the FPECell largely preserved its internal structure (Figure 5K,L).

The unique flame-inhibiting mechanism of phosphazene compounds, along with their molecular tunability, opens a wide design space for the development of next-generation, non-flammable, and high-performance electrolytes for advanced safe batteries.

3.2 | Halogenated Organic Flame-Retardants

This class of flame-retardants primarily includes fluorinated, chlorinated, and brominated organic compounds. Their flame-retardant efficacy generally follows the order: $F > Cl > Br > I$ [175]. The flame-retardant mechanism of halogenated organics involves a thermal decomposition process in which halogen radicals (e.g., $F\cdot$, $Cl\cdot$) are released [176]. These radicals act by scavenging hydrogen ($H\cdot$) and hydroxyl ($OH\cdot$) radicals in the combustion zone, forming non-flammable species such as hydrogen halides or water vapor, thereby terminating the chain reactions of combustion and suppressing flame propagation.

Among them, fluorinated additives are the most widely used because they provide an optimal balance between flame suppression and electrochemical stability. Compared with other halogenated compounds, fluorinated molecules exhibit higher bond energies (C-F), superior thermal and chemical stability, and a wider electrochemical window. At the same time, they show lower volatility and toxicity than Cl, Br, or I analogs, making them much more suitable for practical lithium-ion battery applications.

Fluorinated solvents, including partially or fully fluorinated carbonates and ethers, typically exhibit high flash points, elevated boiling points, and intrinsic non-flammability [177, 178]. The substitution of hydrogen atoms with fluorine atoms not only reduces the combustible hydrogen content, thereby enhancing thermal safety, but also improves the solvent's oxidative stability. The strong electron-withdrawing inductive effect of fluorine raises the electrochemical decomposition voltage of the electrolyte, expanding its oxidative stability window [179], which is particularly beneficial for high-voltage cathode systems. Moreover, fluorinated solvents have been shown to facilitate the formation of more stable SEI on anode surfaces such as silicon and carbon [180], thereby improving interfacial compatibility and battery cycling performance. Some

studies have also demonstrated that certain fluorinated organic solvents can enhance low-temperature performance, further highlighting their multifaceted advantages.

Among halogenated flame-retardant solvents, fluorinated solvents, notably fluorinated carbonates and fluorinated ethers have emerged as particularly promising candidates for improving both the safety and performance of LIBs. Common examples include FEC, 1,1,2,2-tetrafluoroethyl-2,2,3,3-tetrafluoropropyl ether (HFE), bis(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) ether, and 2,2-dimethoxy-4-(trifluoromethyl)-1,3-dioxolane, among others [183].

Smart et al. [184] demonstrated that incorporating a moderate amount of linear carbonate solvents into the electrolyte, especially fluorinated variants, not only enhanced flame retardancy but also facilitated the formation of a dense and effective SEI layer on carbon anodes. This, in turn, improved the reversible capacity and cycling stability of the battery. Wang et al. [32] further proposed a non-flammable electrolyte system composed of TMP, HFE, and LiFSI. The resulting formulation exhibited exceptional flame-retardant behavior (Figure 6A) and supported stable, dendrite-free cycling of lithium metal, with a coulombic efficiency of 99.1% over 500 cycles. Raman spectroscopy confirmed the absence of free solvent molecules, while X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy revealed a LiF-rich interphase on the lithium metal anode, critical for suppressing side reactions and maintaining long-term stability.

Cheng et al. [181] developed a high-voltage resistant electrolyte consisting of 1 M $LiPF_6$ in a mixture of FEC and DEC. In Li||NCM811 full cells, this electrolyte enabled operation over a wide temperature range ($-30^\circ C$ – $70^\circ C$) and maintained high performance under ultrahigh cutoff voltages of 4.7 and 4.8 V. After 160 cycles at 4.7 V, the capacity retention was 95.1%; at 4.8 V, it remained 85.7% after 100 cycles (Figure 6B). Even under lean electrolyte conditions and with an ultrathin ($50\ \mu m$) lithium metal anode, capacity retention reached 89.2% after 150 cycles, demonstrating excellent potential for high energy density applications. Lu et al. [182] synthesized a low-heat-release, non-flammable fluorinated electrolyte based on fluorinated bis(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) carbonate. In commercial pouch-cells undergoing thermal runaway, this electrolyte reduced the peak temperature by one-third and decreased the maximum temperature rise rate from $206.0^\circ C\ s^{-1}$ – $82.6^\circ C\ s^{-1}$ (Figure 6C,D). Moreover, the electrolyte showed excellent compatibility with lithium metal anodes, attributed to the formation of a uniform, CF_3 -rich organic SEI layer. In Li||NCM811 full cells, capacity retention remained as high as 80% after 240 cycles. It is worth noting that at a high energy density of $365\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$, the system retained 90.02% of its capacity after 98 cycles under practical conditions.

In addition to fluorinated compounds, chlorinated and brominated organic solvents have also been explored for their potential as flame-retardant components in battery electrolytes [86]. Chlorine atoms, possessing moderate electron-withdrawing ability, can effectively lower the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energy levels of ether-based solvents when introduced as functional groups, thereby improving oxidative stability while retaining strong lithium-ion solvation capability. Moreover, the presence of chlorine atoms in the molecular

FIGURE 6 | (A) Flammability assessment of the electrolyte. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society [32]. (B) Conceptual illustration of the electrochemical reactions occurring in Li||NCM811 cells when using different electrolyte formulations. Copyright 2022, the Royal Society of Chemistry [181]. (C) Sequential digital images showing the stages (I, II, III) of a nail penetration safety test, along with the final condition (IV) of a Gr||NCM523 pouch cell post-test. Copyright 2023, Elsevier [182]. (D) Infrared thermal images of Gr||NCM523 pouch cells with two types of electrolytes, captured at various time intervals during the nail penetration experiment. Copyright 2023, Elsevier [182].

structure may contribute to the formation of interfacial layers containing both lithium fluoride (LiF) and lithium chloride (LiCl), which can enhance the stability of the SEI. For example, Ren et al. [185] developed a novel chlorinated ether-based electrolyte by substituting traditional 1,2-diethoxyethane (DEE) with chlorine functional groups to synthesize 1,2-bis(2-chloroethoxy) ethane (Cl-DEE). The incorporation of chlorine significantly increased the flash point of DEE from 35°C to 126°C, demonstrating an impressive improvement in flame retardancy while preserving the ether's ability to dissolve high concentrations of lithium salts.

In parallel, Lu et al. [186] introduced a new brominated flame-retardant co-solvent, 2-bromo-1-(2-bromoethoxy)ethane (BBE), specifically aimed at improving flame retardancy and

interfacial compatibility in sodium metal batteries. The bromine-containing additive not only exhibited excellent flame-inhibition behavior, but also facilitated the formation of a bromine-rich SEI layer on the sodium surface, composed primarily of sodium bromide (NaBr). Because of the high ionic conductivity of NaBr [187], this interphase was effective in suppressing dendrite growth and gas evolution, two of the most critical safety challenges in sodium metal battery systems.

These findings highlight the expanding potential of chlorinated and brominated co-solvents as multifunctional additives that simultaneously improve electrolyte safety, electrochemical stability, and electrode compatibility, particularly in emerging alkali metal battery chemistries.

3.3 | Composite Flame-Retardants

Composite flame-retardants typically incorporate two or more flame-retardant elements, which work synergistically to enhance the overall performance of the electrolyte [188]. Common examples include HMPA, pentafluoro (phenoxy) cyclotriphosphazene (FPPN) [189], hexamethylphosphorous triamid, and bis(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)methylphosphonate (BTMP). These multifunctional solvents offer both thermal stability and flame retardancy. For instance, Zhang et al. [168] introduced tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)phosphite into a 1 M LiPF₆ electrolyte based on a PC-EC-EMC solvent system. The addition significantly improved the thermal stability of the electrolyte. Remarkably, when the flame-retardant concentration reached 15%, the electrolyte became essentially non-flammable. Moreover, it suppressed the decomposition of PC, thereby enhancing the coulombic efficiency of the battery to 96%.

In a comprehensive study, Wu et al. [190] investigated a wide range of composite flame-retardant additives. Their findings revealed that combining phosphorus-containing compounds with fluorinated or nitrogen-containing functional groups can yield excellent flame-retardant performance, even at low additive levels (≤ 5 wt.%). Importantly, such combinations do not compromise the electrolyte's ionic conductivity or the battery's cycling stability. Notable examples include the incorporation of triphenyl phosphate (TPP) or perfluorinated phosphazene compounds such as PFPN, both of which demonstrate strong fire suppression capabilities while maintaining electrochemical performance.

Composite flame-retardants represent a promising strategy for enhancing both the safety and electrochemical performance of battery electrolytes [191]. By leveraging the synergistic effects of multiple flame-retardant elements, particularly phosphorus, fluorine, and nitrogen, these additives can achieve high flame resistance at low concentrations without compromising conductivity or cycling stability. This makes them highly attractive for next-generation high-safety battery systems.

4 | Novel Electrolytes

Although the above organophosphorus-based halogenated and composite flame-retardant solvents have demonstrated certain advantages in enhancing flame retardancy, they still face limitations in terms of cost, environmental friendliness, and compatibility with electrode materials. As a result, researchers have turned their attention to more diverse types of novel non-flammable electrolytes, such as ionic liquids, aqueous electrolytes, and solid-state electrolytes. These systems not only offer inherent safety benefits but also open up new possibilities for further improvements in energy density and cycling stability of batteries.

4.1 | Ionic Liquids

ILs have emerged as promising next-generation electrolyte materials in the field of battery technology [192], owing to their

unique physicochemical properties and inherent safety advantages. By definition, ILs are salts that remain in a liquid state at or near room temperature [193, 194], composed entirely of ions, that is, typically large organic cations and either organic or inorganic anions. Unlike conventional organic electrolytes, ILs are non-volatile, non-flammable, and thermally stable, and they exhibit low vapor pressure and excellent environmental compatibility, making them widely recognized as “green solvents”.

From a physical standpoint, ILs are characterized by relatively high viscosities, that is, often one to three orders of magnitude greater than traditional organic solvents [195]. Although this high viscosity can hinder ionic mobility and thus reduce ion transport rates, their outstanding thermal and chemical stability makes them especially suitable for use in harsh or high-temperature electrochemical environments [196]. Furthermore, because of the large size of their constituent ions, ILs generally exhibit lower ionic conductivities compared to low-molecular-weight electrolytes. However, this is compensated by their notably wide electrochemical windows, which can extend up to approximately 4–6 V. This feature is particularly advantageous for the development of high-voltage energy storage systems.

The structural diversity of ILs allows for fine-tuning of their properties to meet the demands of specific battery applications. Based on the cation structure, ILs can be classified into several families [197], for example, imidazolium-based (e.g., 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium, BMIM⁺) [198], piperidinium-based, and pyrrolidinium-based ILs [199]. Commonly used anions include TFSI⁻, FSI⁻, and tetrafluoroborate (BF₄⁻) [200, 201]. Each cation–anion combination confers distinct characteristics in terms of thermal stability, ionic conductivity, and electrochemical window, allowing for customizable electrolyte design based on the operational requirements of various battery chemistries.

In practical applications, ILs are generally employed in two main configurations [205]: (i) Mixed electrolyte systems: In this approach, ILs are blended with metal salts and conventional organic solvents in optimized ratios to balance viscosity and conductivity. These hybrid systems are commonly used to improve the thermal and electrochemical stability of batteries while maintaining practical ion transport. (ii) Neat IL electrolytes: In this case, metal salts such as KPF₆ or NaTFSI are directly dissolved into a pure IL medium to form a fully ionic, nonvolatile, and highly thermally stable electrolyte system. These pure IL-based electrolytes are particularly suited for energy storage devices operating under high-temperature or high-voltage conditions [206, 207].

In previous studies, Yang et al. [34] developed a novel IL-based electrolyte by blending N-propyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (PYR₁₃TFSI) with a conventional EC/DMC electrolyte containing 5% vinylene carbonate (VC). When the IL content reached 60 vol%, the resulting mixed electrolyte surpassed the flammability threshold, rendering it effectively non-flammable (Figure 7A). The study also examined the influence of varying LiTFSI concentrations on the electrochemical performance of LIBs. Although higher concentrations of LiTFSI increased the lithium-ion content in the electrolyte,

FIGURE 7 | (A) Photographs depicting the flammability test setup and results. Copyright 2014, the Electrochemical Society [34]. (B) Cycling stability of a LiFePO_4 cathode using the IL65 electrolyte under elevated temperature conditions. Copyright 2014, the Electrochemical Society [34]. (C) In situ Raman spectroscopy analysis to investigate the redox behavior of C_6O_6 . Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH GmbH [202]. (D) Typical charge/discharge voltage profiles of C_6O_6 at a current density of 20 mA g^{-1} , accompanied by ex situ FTIR spectra at selected states. Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH GmbH [202]. (E, F) Ex situ UV-Vis spectral analysis in two different electrolytes: 1 m LiTFSI in DOL/DME at 25°C (E), and 0.3 m LiTFSI in [PY13][TFSI] at 70°C (F). Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH GmbH [202]. (G) Visual color changes over time in H-cells equipped with either PP or PIL/PP separators. Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH [203]. (H) Diagram illustrating the fabrication process of a composite electrolyte incorporating PIL. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society [204]. (I) Schematic showing the synthesis route and proposed structure of the IL monomer (ILs-Im) and the resulting PIL (PILs-Im). Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society [35].

they also led to a rise in viscosity, which can hinder ionic mobility. The optimal balance between ion transport and viscosity was achieved at a concentration of 0.3 M LiTFSI, where the LiFePO_4 cathode exhibited superior cycling stability and rate capability. As temperature increases, the viscosity of IL-based

electrolytes decreases, whereas ionic conductivity improves. Coupled with their inherently low flammability, these attributes enable IL electrolytes to perform exceptionally well under elevated temperatures, highlighting their potential for high-temperature energy storage applications (Figure 7B).

Yoshii et al. [208] reported a high-voltage PIB electrolyte composed of 0.5 M potassium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)amide (KTFSa) in 1-methyl-1-propylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)amide (PYR₁₃TFSa), enabling safe operation at high voltages [209]. Similarly, Nohira et al. proposed an electrolyte system using K [N(SO₂F)₂] in N-methyl-N-propylpyrrolidinium [N(SO₂F)₂] IL. Their findings demonstrated an impressive ionic conductivity of 4.8 mS cm⁻¹ at 298 K, which outperformed lithium and sodium analogs in the same IL solvent.

More importantly, ILs have shown distinct advantages in organic battery systems. One notable benefit is their ability to reduce the solubility of organic electrode materials compared to conventional electrolytes, thereby improving cycling stability [210]. For example, when using an organic carbonyl compound, cyclohexanone (C₆O₆), as the cathode material in a LIB, and 0.3 M LiTFSI in [PYR₁₃][TFSI] as the electrolyte, the electrochemical reactions were found to be highly reversible, as evidenced by in situ Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy (Figure 7C,D) [202]. Raman spectra showed reversible intensity changes in the C=O stretching vibrations during charge/discharge cycles, consistent with observations from ex situ FTIR measurements. Furthermore, ex situ UV-vis spectroscopy revealed strong absorption peaks throughout the entire cycling process in the conventional 1 M LiTFSI-1,3-Dioxolane/1,2-Dimethoxyethane (LiTFSI-DOL/DME) electrolyte, indicating high solubility of C₆O₆. In contrast, the solubility of C₆O₆ in the 0.3 M LiTFSI-[PYR₁₃][TFSI] system was significantly suppressed, which is beneficial for the long-term stability of organic electrodes (Figure 7E,F).

Polymeric ILs (PILs) represent an important class of functional materials that combine the unique properties of ILs with the mechanical robustness and processability of polymers [211, 212]. PILs are synthesized by polymerizing IL monomers through a variety of methods, including atom transfer radical polymerization, anionic or cationic polymerization, reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer polymerization, and step-growth polymerization. PILs have found wide-ranging applications in battery technologies [213], serving as electrode surface modifiers, solid or gel electrolytes, binders, and interfacial layers at electrode/separator junctions. In these roles, PILs contribute significantly to enhancing interfacial stability between the electrode and electrolyte, suppressing lithium dendrite formation, improving the thermal safety of electrolytes, and promoting selective ion transport.

Compared to conventional ILs, PILs generally suffer from lower ion mobility due to their solid or semi-solid nature and reduced segmental motion [214]. This lower ionic conductivity can be seen as a drawback in certain applications. However, the inherent advantages of PILs [212], for example, excellent thermal stability, wide electrochemical stability windows, non-flammability, and superior safety, make them especially attractive for high-temperature and high-safety battery environments. Furthermore, their ion transport properties can be tuned through rational molecular design. Strategies such as incorporating flexible polymer segments, introducing lithium-ion-coordinating functional groups, or designing nanocomposite structures have been shown to effectively enhance ionic conductivity [215]. For example, the incorporation of polyethylene glycol (PEG) segments into the PIL

backbone can increase the chain flexibility and free volume [216], thereby facilitating faster ion transport. These design strategies open up new possibilities for tailoring PIL-based electrolytes to meet the demanding requirements of next-generation energy storage systems.

Xue et al. [203] developed an anion-exchange membrane by coating commercial PP separators with a PIL layer composed of poly(diallyldimethylammonium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide) (PDADMA⁺TFSI⁻), for use in 3.3 V copper-lithium batteries. As shown in Figure 7G, in an H-type cell using a pristine PP membrane, the right half-cell exhibited a rapid color change to green, which intensified over time, indicating copper ion migration across the membrane. In contrast, the H-cell equipped with a PIL/PP separator remained colorless even after 24 h, demonstrating that the PIL coating effectively suppresses Cu²⁺ crossover through the membrane.

In another study, Ma et al. [204] synthesized a PIL by polymerizing 1-vinyl-3-ethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide ([VEIm][TFSI]) in a one-step procedure. The resulting PIL was then blended with LiTFSI and Li_{1.3}Al_{0.3}Ti_{1.7}(PO₄)₃ (LATP) ceramic electrolyte particles, followed by casting into a polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fiber matrix to fabricate a composite polymer electrolyte (Figure 7H). At a LiTFSI content of 2.0 mol kg⁻¹, the composite electrolyte achieved ionic conductivities of 7.78 × 10⁻⁵ S cm⁻¹ at 30°C and 5.92 × 10⁻⁴ S cm⁻¹ at 60°C, values considered adequate for practical LIB applications. When used in an all-solid-state LiFePO₄/PIL-LiTFSI/Li cell operated at 60°C and 1C rate, the initial discharge capacity was 138.4 mAh g⁻¹, and 90% of that capacity was retained after 250 cycles. In particular, the battery employing the PIL-LiTFSI-LATP composite electrolyte showed only a 3.6% capacity loss after 250 cycles (from 141.3 to 136.2 mAh g⁻¹), underscoring the excellent thermal and cycling durability of the system under elevated temperatures.

Wang et al. [35] further introduced a novel class of microporous imidazolium-based PILs (PILs-Im) as high-capacity anode materials for lithium-ion storage (Figure 7I). These materials consisted of imidazole and triazine ring-linked moieties, which were electrochemically active and capable of reversibly storing lithium ions. Additionally, the presence of methylene groups in conjugation with the aromatic structure facilitated efficient electron transport through the polymer backbone. As an anode material, PILs-Im delivered a high specific capacity of 846.6 mAh g⁻¹ at 100 mA g⁻¹, and retained 165 mAh g⁻¹ even at an ultrahigh current density of 10 A g⁻¹. It is worth noting that after 500 cycles at 1.0 A g⁻¹, the material exhibited almost no capacity degradation, confirming its outstanding long-term stability.

4.2 | Aqueous Electrolytes

Aqueous electrolytes have garnered increasing attention as a highly promising class of electrolyte systems due to their intrinsic advantages [217, 218], including abundant raw material availability, low cost, non-flammability, and strong sustainability and environmental compatibility [219, 220]. These characteristics make aqueous electrolytes especially well-suited for large-scale

energy storage applications such as grid load leveling, renewable energy integration, and stationary storage systems [221, 222]. Compared with conventional organic electrolytes, aqueous electrolytes offer a significantly enhanced safety profile. Their non-flammable and thermally stable nature greatly reduces the risk of thermal runaway [223], particularly under extreme conditions such as elevated temperatures, short circuits, or mechanical damage. This intrinsic safety makes them ideal for deployment in scenarios requiring high operational reliability and low hazard potential [224, 225]. Moreover, water, as the solvent, is nontoxic and poses virtually no environmental burden [226], further reinforcing the ecological appeal of aqueous systems in the context of green and sustainable energy technologies. As the global push for carbon neutrality and renewable energy accelerates [227], the environmental friendliness of aqueous electrolytes positions them as a strategic alternative for next-generation battery chemistries, particularly in applications where safety, cost, and ecological impact are prioritized over energy density.

In 1994, Dahn et al. [228] pioneered the concept of aqueous LIBs by reporting a system composed of a spinel-type LiMn_2O_3 cathode, a VO_2 anode, and a 5 mol L^{-1} aqueous lithium nitrate (LiNO_3) electrolyte. This foundational work marked the beginning of research into aqueous LIBs and holds significant historical importance in the field of electrochemical energy storage. In this system, LiMn_2O_4 was selected as the cathode material due to its high operating voltage ($\sim 4 \text{ V}$ vs. Li^+/Li , though notably lower in aqueous systems) and robust structural stability. VO_2 , with its layered structure and moderate lithiation potential, was employed as the anode to facilitate reversible lithium-ion intercalation and deintercalation. Despite these advantages, a fundamental limitation of conventional aqueous electrolytes is their intrinsically narrow electrochemical stability window [229], typically restricted to $\sim 1.23 \text{ V}$. This constraint arises from the thermodynamic decomposition of water into oxygen (O_2) at the cathode and hydrogen (H_2) at the anode when the cell voltage exceeds this limit [230–232]. Such parasitic gas evolution not only reduces energy efficiency but also poses safety risks, particularly in sealed systems.

This narrow voltage window has historically hindered the development of aqueous systems capable of achieving high energy density and high-voltage operation [233, 234]. In recent years, however, innovative electrolyte engineering strategies, most notably the “water-in-salt” concept, have successfully broadened the electrochemical window of aqueous systems up to approximately 3 V (Figure 8A) [33, 237]. In WiSE formulations, the salt concentration is so high that the number of free water molecules per cation becomes extremely limited. For instance, in a 21 M LiTFSI -based solution, the $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{lithium-ion}$ ratio is only 2.6, meaning that the electrostatic field generated by the lithium-ion is no longer sufficiently screened by water molecules (Figure 8B). Consequently, water molecules are partially displaced by anionic components in the lithium-ion solvation shell, effectively suppressing the electrochemical activity of water and mitigating decomposition reactions.

Building on this principle, Yamada et al. [235] proposed the concept of hydrate-melt electrolytes, wherein a highly concentrated ternary mixture of lithium bis(pentafluoroethanesulfonyl)imide (LiBETI), lithium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide ($\text{LiN}(\text{SO}_2\text{C}_2\text{F}_5)_2$), and water was

formulated in a molar ratio of 7:3:20 (Figure 8C,D). This unique electrolyte system exhibited a remarkably wide electrochemical stability window, extending from 1.25 to 5.05 V versus Li/Li^+ , a total of 3.8 V . Such expansion not only enables the utilization of higher-voltage electrode materials in aqueous environments but also redefines the potential of water-based batteries in high-energy and high-power applications.

In addition to high-concentration strategies such as “water-in-salt” and hydrate-melt electrolytes, the introduction of water-confined additives has emerged as an effective approach to suppress the activity of water molecules and extend the electrochemical stability window [224, 238, 239]. Xie et al. [236] developed a novel molecularly crowded aqueous electrolyte, in which water molecules are confined within a PEG network via hydrogen bonding, enabling a high working voltage of up to 3.2 V (Figure 8E,F). Their study revealed that, compared to the oxygen atoms in water, the ether oxygen atoms in PEG carry a higher negative charge density due to the electron-donating effect of adjacent alkyl groups. As a result, the hydrogen bonds formed between PEG and water molecules were weaker than those between two water molecules. This weak hydrogen bonding strengthened the O–H covalent bonds within water molecules, thereby reducing their tendency to participate in electrolysis reactions. In such a molecularly crowded environment, virtually all water molecules were engaged in hydrogen bonding with PEG, leaving little to no “free” water available. This confinement elevated the overpotential required to initiate water decomposition reactions, that is, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER), thereby significantly expanding the electrochemical stability window.

Similarly, Bi et al. [240] introduced sucrose as a hydrogen-bonding additive in a dilute 2 M NaNO_3 electrolyte, achieving an expanded stability window of approximately 2.8 V . The hydroxyl-rich structure of sucrose allows for strong hydrogen bonding with water molecules, disrupting the tetrahedral coordination network of bulk water and reducing the amount of free water present. This effectively suppresses HER and OER processes by altering the local solvation environment.

Despite these promising advancements, aqueous electrolytes remain fundamentally constrained by the thermodynamic properties of water itself [241]. The relatively low decomposition potential of water places inherent limits on the energy density that aqueous batteries can achieve. Consequently, although substantial progress has been made in the development of rechargeable aqueous battery systems [242–244], most reported configurations still fall short of meeting the comprehensive requirements for practical application, for example, competitive energy density, long cycle life, and seamless system integration. As a result, widespread commercial deployment of aqueous batteries remains limited at present.

4.3 | Solid-State Electrolytes

SSEs are a critical component of all-solid-state batteries [245–247], with their properties directly influencing key performance metrics such as energy density, safety, and cycle life. Depending

FIGURE 8 | (A) Conceptual diagram illustrating the widened electrochemical stability window in water-in-salt electrolytes and the resulting shifts in redox potentials of the LiMn_2O_4 cathode and Mo_6S_8 anode due to increased salt concentration. Copyright 2015, American Association for the Advancement of Science [33]. (B) Illustration showing changes in the primary solvation shell of lithium-ion when transitioning from dilute to water-in-salt electrolyte environments. Copyright 2015, American Association for the Advancement of Science [33]. (C) Phase diagram (liquidus line) of $\text{Li}(\text{TFSI})_x(\text{BETI})_{1-x}/(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ salt-water mixtures. Copyright 2016, Springer Nature [235]. (D) Composition details, molar amounts of LiTFSI, LiBETI, and water, used to create the $\text{Li}(\text{TFSI})_{0.7}(\text{BETI})_{0.3}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ hydrate melt, with red arrows indicating the corresponding liquid levels. Copyright 2016, Springer Nature [235]. (E) Comparison of the redox potentials of common LIB electrode materials with the electrochemical stability ranges of different electrolytes. Copyright 2020, Springer Nature [236]. (F) Electrochemical stability windows of various electrolytes were determined through linear sweep voltammetry. Copyright 2020, Springer Nature [236].

on their material composition and ion conduction mechanisms, SSEs can be broadly classified into three major categories: (i) Organic polymer SSEs; (ii) inorganic SSEs; and (iii) composite SSEs. Each type of SSE offers distinct advantages and faces specific challenges, as illustrated in Figure 9A [30]. Consequently, their development trajectories and application potential vary significantly across different battery technologies and operational scenarios. Polymer electrolytes are typically favored for their mechanical flexibility and processability, whereas inorganic electrolytes offer high ionic conductivity and excellent electrochemical stability. Composite electrolytes aim to integrate the benefits of both classes, striving to overcome the limitations of each.

Compared with inorganic SSEs, polymer SSEs generally offer superior flexibility, facile processability, and favorable interfacial compatibility with electrodes, making them attractive candidates for solid-state metal batteries [250]. Nevertheless, their distinct structural characteristics result in different ion transport mechanisms from those of inorganic SSEs, often leading to lower ionic conductivity. Moreover, the high-molecular-weight compounds produced during monomer polymerization are prone to poor thermal stability, which further limits performance. According to their composition and solvent content, polymer SSEs are typically classified into two categories: all-solid polymer electrolytes and gel polymer electrolytes.

FIGURE 9 | (A) Radar charts illustrate the comparative performance metrics of various SSEs. Copyright 2023, Elsevier [30]. (B) Schematic diagram of polymer chains interconnecting. (C) HRTEM images of the CEI layer from the cycled NCM622 particles. Copyright 2023, Elsevier [248]. (D) Chemical structures of polymer electrolytes and salt. (E) Schematic illustration of microstructures (EO10-CTRL and EO10-PFPE electrolytes). (F, G) Cross-sectional (F) and surface (G) SEM images of EO10-PFPE composite SPE. Copyright 2022, Springer Nature [249].

Commonly studied all-solid polymer SSEs include those based on poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO), poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), PVDF-co-hexafluoropropylene (PVDF-HFP), and polyacrylonitrile (PAN) matrices [251, 252]. Among these, PEO-based electrolytes have received the most attention [253]. This is primarily attributed to the high segmental flexibility and polarity of the ethylene oxide (EO) units within the polymer backbone, which can solvate lithium salts and facilitate the formation of continuous ionic conduction pathways. As a result, PEO electrolytes exhibit relatively high ionic conductivity under moderate to elevated temperatures (typically above 60°C) [254]. However, all-solid polymer systems still face several key limitations: (i) Low ionic conductivity at room temperature. Typical systems such as linear PEO-based electrolytes usually exhibit ionic conductivities of only 10^{-7} to 10^{-5} S cm⁻¹, which is far below the $\sim 10^{-3}$ S cm⁻¹ level of liquid electrolytes. This limitation mainly arises from the restricted mobility of polymer chain segments at low temperatures, which hinders the formation of continuous pathways for lithium-ion transport. (ii) Another drawback is the issue of crystallinity. The highly ordered arrangement of polymer chains can easily lead to local crystallization, which creates nonconductive domains and further reduces ionic conductivity. (iii) Polymer electrolytes also

face interfacial instability. When in contact with high-voltage cathodes, they are prone to oxidative decomposition, while at the lithium metal anode side, unstable SEI may form, often inducing lithium dendrite growth. (iv) In addition, they generally exhibit insufficient mechanical strength and thermal stability. Pure polymer matrices tend to soften or degrade at elevated temperatures or during long-term cycling, which makes it difficult to suppress dendrite penetration effectively.

To overcome these limitations, one common strategy is molecular structure design and modification. Approaches such as introducing branched or cross-linked polymers can reduce crystallinity and improve chain mobility. In a related study [248], researchers proposed an ultrathin cross-linked polymer SSE constructed from PEO/LiTFSI with tetraethylene glycol dimethyl ether (TEGDME) and LiODFB as an additive (Figure 9B). The crosslinking was triggered by photoinitiated radicals originating from methylene groups, which promoted both PEO-TEGDME linkages and TEGDME oligomerization, thereby yielding a dual-network structure. The in situ polymerization at the electrode/electrolyte interface enabled intimate interfacial contact and produced a highly amorphous matrix. As a result, the electrolyte achieved a Li⁺ transference

number of 0.79, a wide electrochemical stability window of 4.8 V, and an ionic conductivity of 0.57 mS cm^{-1} at 30°C . The dual-salt system (LiTFSI and LiDFOB) facilitated the formation of a robust LiF-enriched cathode electrolyte interface (CEI) layer (Figure 9C), effectively suppressing PEO degradation under high-voltage conditions. When paired with a high-voltage NCM622 cathode, the Li/SPE/NCM622 cell retained 94.7% of its initial capacity after 100 cycles at 4.2 V and 30°C . Block copolymers are also widely studied, in which one phase provides mechanical strength while the other ensures ionic conduction. Wang et al. [249] developed a solvent-free solid polymer electrolyte for all-solid-state SIBs by introducing a block copolymer in which PEO chains were terminated with perfluoropolyether (PFPE). The chemical structures and corresponding nanostructures of the PFPE-modified polymer (EO10-PFPE) and the reference polymer (EO10-CTRL) are presented in Figure 9D,E. When incorporated into a PVDF matrix, the EO10-PFPE electrolyte completely infiltrated the pores, producing a flexible and solvent-free polymer electrolyte, as illustrated in Figure 9F,G. Compared with conventional PEO-based polymer electrolytes, this architecture demonstrated superior performance by enabling nanostructural self-assembly that preserved a high storage modulus even at elevated temperatures. The PEO domains provided efficient ion transport pathways under high salt concentrations ($\text{EO}/\text{Na}^+ = 4$), whereas the incorporation of PFPE segments markedly increased the Na^+ transference number to 0.46 at 80°C and promoted the formation of a stable solid-electrolyte interphase. In addition, incorporating ionic liquids or plasticizers has been shown to enhance lithium-ion transport while maintaining flexibility [255]. Das et al. [256] investigated the effect of various plasticizers, including PC, EC, and DMC, on the ionic conductivity of PEO-LiClO₄ polymer SSEs. Their findings indicated that the dielectric constant of the plasticizer plays a critical role in enhancing the ionic conductivity of the resulting gel polymer electrolytes. High-permittivity plasticizers promote the dissociation of lithium salts or ion pairs in the PEO matrix, increasing the number of free mobile lithium-ion and thereby improving ionic conductivity. However, as Hassoun et al. [257] pointed out, the introduction of liquid-phase components can compromise the electrochemical stability of polymer electrolytes. Nonetheless, specific additives such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) have been shown to extend the electrochemical stability window of PEO-based systems from 3.9 to 4.1 V (vs. Li/Li⁺), offering a promising trade-off between conductivity and stability.

Another important direction is the use of inorganic filler composites, such as Al₂O₃, TiO₂, SiO₂, or ion-conductive ceramics such as LAGP (Li_{1.5}Al_{0.5}Ge_{1.5}(PO₄)₃) [258–260]. These fillers can suppress polymer crystallization, create additional lithium-ion transport pathways, and simultaneously improve mechanical strength and thermal stability.

Gel polymer SSEs combine the advantages of liquid electrolytes and solid polymer electrolytes by integrating liquid plasticizers or solvents into a polymer-salt matrix. In this configuration, the liquid phase is confined within the polymer framework, thereby reducing leakage risks while simultaneously providing high ionic conductivity and excellent interfacial compatibility, together with improved safety and dendrite suppression. Since

the pioneering work of Perche et al. [261] in 1975 on thermoplastic gels, significant progress has been made in both understanding and tailoring gel electrolytes. Poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO), widely used in all-solid polymer electrolytes, also serves as a common matrix for gel systems, where optimized formulations can deliver ionic conductivities on the order of 10^{-3} – $10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. Although conventional plasticizers may compromise mechanical strength and thermal stability, strategies such as polymer crosslinking and the incorporation of poly (ionic liquids) have proven effective in enhancing robustness while maintaining high conductivity. Recent advances, including composite and plastic-crystal-based gels, further demonstrate how rational molecular design can suppress electrolyte leakage, stabilize cation transport pathways, and mitigate polarization under high current densities. Owing to this unique integration of safety and electrochemical performance, gel SSEs remain at the forefront of research and hold strong promise for practical application in high-energy metal batteries.

In comparison to their polymer counterparts, inorganic SSEs have attracted increasing attention due to their inherently higher room-temperature ionic conductivity and larger Li⁺ transference numbers [262]. Additionally, these materials typically exhibit superior mechanical strength, which is critical for suppressing the growth of dendrites, an issue commonly encountered in metal anode systems. This mechanical rigidity contributes significantly to the enhanced safety of batteries employing inorganic SSEs. Currently, the most widely studied inorganic SSEs can be broadly categorized into oxide-based, sulfide-based, and halide-based SSEs [263–265]. However, despite these advantages, inorganic SSEs face several intrinsic challenges, including interfacial instability with both cathode and anode materials [266, 267], and loss of physical contact with electrode materials. Chemical or electrochemical reactions at the interface can lead to the formation of unwanted intermediate phases, which act as barriers to lithium-ion conduction. This interfacial degradation not only increases resistance but also compromises the long-term cycling stability and rate capability of the battery. [268, 269]. In addition, the stresses that accumulate in electrode materials during electrochemical cycling render these point contacts particularly fragile, often resulting in crack formation, crack propagation, and even interface delamination [270].

Oxide-based SSEs, including NASICON, perovskite and garnet structures, have been extensively investigated due to their outstanding chemical stability and wide electrochemical windows. Among them, NASICON-type and garnet-type electrolytes are the most widely applied. NASICON-type electrolytes possess stable structures and excellent properties; the most common examples include Li₂O–Al₂O₃–TiO₂–P₂O₅ (LATP) and Li₂O–Al₂O₃–GeO₂–P₂O₅ (LAGP), with LATP generally exhibiting higher ionic conductivity than LAGP [271]. In the case of garnet-type electrolytes, Li₇La₃Zr₂O₁₂ (LLZO)-based solid electrolytes demonstrate the highest conductivity among lithium-containing garnets, reaching approximately $10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature [272]. Although this value is lower than that of NASICON-type electrolytes, LLZO shows better stability against lithium metal. Similarly, Li_{6.55}Ga_{0.15}La₃Zr₂O₁₂, another

garnet-type electrolyte, also exhibits very high conductivity, up to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. However, the high interfacial resistance between oxide SSEs and electrodes, along with their brittle nature and processing challenges, remain a major obstacle to their large-scale application. To address this, Zhang et al. [262] introduced a novel multifunctional hybrid interlayer at the LAGP/Li interface, composed of $\text{Li}_{6.4}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_{1.4}\text{Ta}_{0.6}\text{O}_{12}$ ionic fillers and poly (ionic liquid) electrolyte (HILP), as shown in Figure 10A. The HILP exhibited strong lithiophilicity, excellent thermal stability, and provided continuous Li^+ conduction pathways across the interface. By stabilizing the interface and inducing the formation of an SEI, the HILP-LAGP configuration achieved a high critical current density of 1.4 mA cm^{-2} and delivered prolonged cycling stability without lithium dendrite formation. Furthermore, this binder not only ensured sufficient mechanical strength and strong adhesion to active, conductive, and current collector materials but also offered excellent processability. As a result, the full cells delivered a reversible capacity of 146 mAh g^{-1} at 0.3 C .

Sulfide-based SSEs have emerged as a major focus of research [276, 277], owing to their liquid-like ionic conductivities

($> 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ in some cases) and excellent interfacial wettability with electrode materials. These properties facilitate more efficient ion transport across interfaces and reduce interfacial resistance. Compounds such as $\text{Li}_{10}\text{GeP}_2\text{S}_{12}$ (LGPS) and argyrodite-type electrolytes demonstrate excellent ion transport and favorable electrode wettability, enabling intimate electrode-electrolyte contact and low interfacial resistance. Moreover, these materials are relatively soft, which allows them to be densified at room temperature under moderate pressure, making fabrication more practical. Zhou et al. [273] introduced a low-melting molecular crystal, $\text{S}_{9.3}\text{I}$ (melting point $\sim 65^\circ\text{C}$), as a self-healing cathode material that can periodically re-melt during battery cycling, thereby repairing interfacial damage and maintaining contact with the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ electrolyte (Figure 10B,C). This Li- $\text{S}_{9.3}\text{I}$ system demonstrated remarkable cycling stability, achieving over 400 stable cycles with a capacity retention of 87%, highlighting the potential of thermally adaptive materials in interface management. Zeng et al. [29] investigated a series of chlorine-doped sulfide-based electrolytes, $\text{Li}_{7-x}\text{PS}_{6-x}\text{Cl}_x$ ($x = 0.6, 1.0, 1.3, 1.45, \text{ and } 1.6$), and found that the composition with $x = 1.3$ produced the most favorable interfacial structure. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-

FIGURE 10 | (A) Schematic illustrations of interface evaluation in LAGP-based solid batteries with and without the HILP layer. Copyright 2025, Elsevier [262]. (B, C) Cross-sectional SEM images showing the $\text{S}_{9.3}\text{I}$ cathode/SSE interface at 25°C : after 50 charge/discharge cycles (B) and following thermal treatment at 100°C post-cycling (C). Copyright 2024, Springer Nature [273]. (D) SEM and EDS cross-sectional images comparing Cl-06 and Cl-13 samples. Copyright 2022, Springer Nature [29]. (E) Calculated thermodynamic electrochemical windows of different electrolytes. Copyright 2019, Wiley [274]. (F) The crystal structures of $\alpha\text{-Li}_2\text{ZrCl}_6$ (a) and $\beta\text{-Li}_2\text{ZrCl}_6$. Copyright 2021, Springer Nature [275].

dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) of cross-sectional regions (Figure 10D) revealed the formation of a dense, uniform, and compositionally consistent SEI, primarily composed of LiCl. This interphase significantly reduced interfacial resistance and contributed to improved electrochemical performance, demonstrating the effectiveness of in situ SEI engineering in mitigating interface-related limitations.

Halide-based SSEs have recently emerged as a promising new class of solid electrolytes. Owing to their highly flexible anion sublattices, halides such as Li_3InCl_6 and Li_3YCl_6 exhibit decent ionic conductivities (10^{-3} – 10^{-4} S cm^{-1}) and wide electrochemical windows. Importantly, halide electrolytes often demonstrate good compatibility with high-voltage cathode materials, enabling stable cycling at voltages above 4 V. Compared with oxide- and sulfide-based SSEs, halides possess higher electrochemical redox potentials. For example, fluorine has a formation potential of +2.87 V versus SHE, far exceeding the oxygen evolution potential (+1.23 V vs. SHE), which explains the superior electrochemical stability of fluoride-based electrolytes (Figure 10E) [274]. In addition, their relatively high deformability compared with oxides also improves interfacial contact. However, their limited mechanical robustness and sensitivity to moisture still present. To address this, Wang et al. [275] developed a Li_2ZrCl_6 electrolyte that shows remarkable resistance to humidity, maintaining its ionic conductivity without detectable moisture absorption even after exposure to 5% relative humidity (Figure 10F). Li_2ZrCl_6 is synthesized from raw materials that are orders of magnitude cheaper than those required for advanced chloride solid electrolytes; however, it simultaneously achieves a high ionic conductivity of 0.81 mS cm^{-1} at room temperature, excellent deformability, and stable operation with 4 V-class cathodes.

In summary, Table 4 presents a comparative overview of the three major categories of inorganic solid-state electrolytes, namely oxides, sulfides, and halides. Their respective advantages and limitations are systematically outlined, highlighting

the trade-offs between ionic conductivity, electrochemical stability, mechanical robustness, and interfacial compatibility. This comparison not only emphasizes the unique strengths of each electrolyte family but also illustrates the challenges that remain to be addressed for their practical implementation in solid-state batteries.

Composite SSEs are regarded as one of the most promising next-generation materials for high-performance solid-state batteries [278], as they integrate the complementary advantages of both organic polymer electrolytes and inorganic SSEs. Based on the distribution of inorganic and polymeric phases, composite solid electrolytes are commonly grouped into two categories: (i) ceramic fillers dispersed within a polymer/lithium salt system (ceramic in polymer), and (ii) polymer/lithium salt phases dispersed within an inorganic electrolyte framework (polymer in ceramic). On one hand, composite SSEs inherit the mechanical flexibility, excellent processability, and favorable interfacial contact of polymer electrolytes, helping to alleviate interfacial issues commonly encountered at the electrode–electrolyte interface. On the other hand, the inclusion of inorganic components imparts higher ionic conductivity, improved thermal stability, and enhanced mechanical strength—collectively boosting the overall electrochemical performance and safety of the system. As a result, composite SSEs are capable of delivering adequate ionic conductivity over a broad temperature range while maintaining strong interfacial compatibility with electrodes [279]. This unique combination of properties makes composite SSEs key enablers for achieving solid-state batteries with high energy density, extended cycle life, and superior safety.

For example, Zhang et al. [280] introduced a three-dimensional (3D) metal-organic framework-filled (MOF-filled) composite SSEs based on a PEO matrix, targeting lithium-sulfur battery systems. As illustrated in Figure 11A, the orderly arrangement of MOFs with optimized pore size effectively restricted the polysulfide shuttle effect, a major challenge in lithium-sulfur

TABLE 4 | Comparison of three major inorganic solid-state electrolytes.

Type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Oxide-based SSEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Excellent chemical stability and wide electrochemical window ii. High mechanical strength and effective dendrite suppression iii. Highly stable in air, no need for inert gas synthesis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. High interfacial resistance with electrodes ii. Brittle nature and poor processability
Sulfide-based SSEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Ionic conductivity comparable to or exceeding liquid electrolytes ($> 10^{-2}$ S cm^{-1}) ii. Good interfacial wettability with electrodes, low interfacial resistance iii. Soft nature allows densification at room temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Poor stability in air (sensitive to $\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) ii. Limited electrochemical stability against high voltage cathodes
Halide-based SSEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Decent ionic conductivity (10^{-3}–10^{-4} S cm^{-1}) ii. Wide electrochemical window, compatible with high voltage cathodes iii. Better deformability than oxides, improving interfacial contact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Limited mechanical strength ii. Moisture sensitivity, requiring strict handling

batteries. In contrast, conventional polymer-based composite SSEs, as shown in Figure 11B,C, struggle with issues such as poor lithium polysulfide suppression, uneven lithium flux, and limited lithium salt dissociation. The 3D MOF-filled composite SSEs address these problems through a dense and interconnected 3D microporous membrane. This architecture enhances both lithium flux uniformity and LiTFSI dissociation, while simultaneously mitigating the shuttle effect of LiPS. Liang et al. [281] developed a dual-layered composite electrolyte by coating both sides of a LAMP ceramic sheet with a PAN/PEO-based polymer matrix. This design enabled a soft and stable interface between the electrode and the SSEs, entirely preventing direct contact between LAMP and lithium metal. The use of a high-mechanical-strength LAMP ceramic core enhanced the structural robustness of the electrolyte, whereas its high lithium-ion conductivity facilitated uniform lithium-ion distribution, effectively suppressing the formation of interfacial space charge layers (Figure 11D,E). Zheng et al. [282] prepared PEO-based composite solid electrolytes by incorporating one-

dimensional $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ nanofibers (LLZO-NFs). Rapid liquid nitrogen quenching suppressed the regular packing of PEO chains, converting more regions into an amorphous phase and creating additional Li^+ transport pathways (Figure 11F). As a result, the ionic conductivity increased more than threefold, with a Li^+ transference number of 0.61 at 45°C . Besides quenching, reducing polymer crystallinity can also be achieved by copolymerization, grafting mobile side chains, or blending polymers with good mutual compatibility.

5 | Summary and Perspective

With the ever-growing demand for high-performance and intrinsically safe energy storage systems, the development of non-flammable electrolytes has emerged as a critical direction for LIBs, SIBs, and PIBs. This review has systematically outlined the underlying safety challenges of conventional carbonate-based

FIGURE 11 | (A–C) Illustrative schematics of three types of composite SSEs: 3D MPPL CSE (A), PL CSE (B), and MPL CSE (C). Copyright 2024, American Association for the Advancement of Science [280]. (D, E) Illustrations of the solid full battery with (D) pristine LAMP and (E) DPCE. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society [281]. (F) Schematic of the electrolyte. Copyright 2021, Elsevier [282].

electrolyte systems, particularly their susceptibility to thermal runaway and flammability under abuse conditions. In response to these challenges, recent advancements in flame-retardant additives, organophosphorus and halogenated solvents, ILs, aqueous formulations, and SSEs have demonstrated promising pathways toward enhancing battery safety without sacrificing electrochemical performance. A summary of their basic properties is presented in Figure 12A–F. Among the various strategies discussed, the design of inherently non-flammable electrolyte systems, particularly those based on fluorinated solvents, phosphate esters, and ILs, offers compelling advantages in suppressing combustion, stabilizing electrode interfaces, and enabling high-voltage operations. Moreover, the emergence of hybrid systems such as water-in-salt aqueous electrolytes, PILs, and composite SSEs suggests that multifunctional approaches integrating thermal stability, ionic conductivity, and interfacial compatibility may represent the most viable route for future high-safety battery systems. Looking forward, several critical challenges need be addressed to translating laboratory advancements into commercially viable technologies:

- i. **Interfacial stability:** Many non-flammable electrolytes, such as high-concentration electrolytes, phosphates, and fluorinated solvents, still undergo parasitic reactions at high-voltage cathodes or metal anodes, leading to capacity fading with functional groups such as -F, -CN, or -SO₂- to improve electrochemical robustness while leveraging in situ and operando characterization techniques to gain deeper insight into interfacial evolution. These efforts will enable the design of electrolytes compatible with high-voltage cathodes (e.g., Ni-rich cathodes) and lithium/sodium/potassium metal anodes.
- ii. **Balancing safety and performance:** Although the incorporation of flame-retardant components effectively enhances thermal safety, it frequently results in increased viscosity or reduced ionic conductivity, thereby compromising rate capability. To overcome this trade-off, rational molecular engineering strategies, as well as hybrid electrolyte systems such as localized high-concentration electrolytes, gels, or dual-solvent formulations, should be explored. Such approaches will help achieve intrinsic flame retardancy without sacrificing high energy density or long cycle life.
- iii. **Scalability and cost efficiency:** Scalability and cost remain critical barriers to practical deployment. Many promising candidates, including ILs, high-concentration electrolytes, and multi-component additive systems, are hindered by high material costs and complex synthesis routes. Addressing this issue requires the development of green and sustainable synthesis strategies based on low-cost or renewable precursors, along with techno-economic assessments to guide large-scale implementation. These advances will be essential for enabling the widespread adoption of non-flammable electrolytes in electric vehicles and grid-scale energy storage.
- iv. **Advanced characterization and modeling:** A deeper mechanistic understanding of non-flammable electrolytes is also urgently needed. Their thermal stability, decomposition mechanisms, and failure pathways remain insufficiently understood, limiting rational optimization. Future studies should employ advanced diagnostic tools such as in situ calorimetry, thermal analysis of full cells, and operando spectroscopy, in combination with multi-scale computational modeling, including molecular dynamics, density functional theory, and multiphysics simulations. These complementary approaches will accelerate electrolyte design and reduce reliance on empirical trial-and-error strategies.
- v. **Application-specific optimization:** It is important to recognize that no single electrolyte formulation will meet

FIGURE 12 | (A–F) Radar diagrams of various non-flammable electrolyte systems.

the diverse demands of all application scenarios. Portable electronics require safe electrolytes that support fast charging in thin-format cells, electric vehicles demand wide-temperature operability and long-term cycling stability, whereas grid storage systems prioritize cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability. Future research should therefore embrace application-specific optimization strategies to tailor electrolyte properties to the requirements of each use case, thereby bridging the gap between laboratory innovation and practical implementation.

In conclusion, although substantial progress has been made in developing nonflammable electrolytes, future breakthroughs will depend on interdisciplinary collaboration across materials science, electrochemistry, thermal engineering, and system integration. These advances will be pivotal in realizing intrinsically safe, high-performance, and sustainable batteries for a broad range of applications.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. R. Meys, A. Kätelhön, M. Bachmann, et al., "Achieving Net-Zero Greenhouse Gas Emission Plastics by a Circular Carbon Economy," *Science* 374, no. 6563 (2021): 71–76, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abg9853>.
2. V. Foster, P. A. Trotter, S. Werner, et al., "Development Transitions for Fossil Fuel-Producing Low and Lower-Middle Income Countries in a Carbon-Constrained World," *Nature Energy* 9, no. 3 (2024): 242–250, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01440-3>.
3. R. M. Almeida, A.-U.-H. Chowdhury, H. Rodrigo, M. Li, and R. J. P. Schmitt, "Offsetting the Greenhouse Gas Footprint of Hydropower With Floating Solar Photovoltaics," *Nature Sustainability* 7, no. 9 (2024): 1102–1106, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01384-w>.
4. P. Achakulwisut, P. Erickson, C. Guivarch, R. Schaeffer, E. Brutschin, and S. Pye, "Global Fossil Fuel Reduction Pathways Under Different Climate Mitigation Strategies and Ambitions," *Nature Communications* 14, no. 1 (2023): 5425, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41105-z>.
5. N. Soni, P. K. Singh, S. Mallick, et al., "Advancing Sustainable Energy: Exploring New Frontiers and Opportunities in the Green Transition," *Advanced Sustainable Systems* 8, no. 10 (2024): 2400160, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advsu.202400160>.
6. Y. Song, S. Fang, N. Xu, et al., "Solar Transpiration-Powered Lithium Extraction and Storage," *Science* 385, no. 6716 (2024): 1444–1449, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adm7034>.
7. J. Wang, X. Cao, X. Cui, et al., "Recent Advances of Green Electricity Generation: Potential in Solar Interfacial Evaporation System," *Advances in Materials* 36, no. 16 (2024): 2311151, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202311151>.
8. H. Mai, T. C. Le, D. Chen, D. A. Winkler, and R. A. Caruso, "Machine Learning in the Development of Adsorbents for Clean Energy Application and Greenhouse Gas Capture," *Advanced Science* 9, no. 36 (2022): 2203899, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202203899>.
9. S. Zhang, Z. Wu, Z. Liu, and Z. Hu, "An Emerging Energy Technology: Self-Uninterrupted Electricity Power Harvesting From the Sun and Cold Space," *Advanced Energy Materials* 13, no. 19 (2023): 2300260, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202300260>.
10. R. Chen and G.-M. Weng, "Sustainable Energy Resources for Driving Methane Conversion," *Advanced Energy Materials* 13, no. 36 (2023): 2301734, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202301734>.
11. C. de Oliveira Costa Souza Rosa, E. da Silva Christo, K. A. Costa, and Ld Santos, "Assessing Complementarity and Optimising the Combination of Intermittent Renewable Energy Sources Using Ground Measurements," *Journal of Cleaner Production* 258 (2020): 120946, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120946>.
12. T. R. Ayodele and A. S. O. Ogunjuyigbe, "Mitigation of Wind Power Intermittency: Storage Technology Approach," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 44 (2015): 447–456, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.034>.
13. Y. Yao, S. Wang, X. Ma, et al., "Iridium Cluster Decoration on Amorphous Cobalt Oxide-Coated Carbon Nanotubes for High-Performance Lithium-Oxygen Battery Cathodes," *Small* 21, no. 33 (2025): 2503521, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202503521>.
14. H. Zhang, M. Sun, F. Sun, et al., "High-Efficiency and High-Capacity Aqueous Electrochromic Energy Storage Devices Enabled by Decoupled Titanium Oxide/Viologen Derivative Hybrid Materials," *Research: Ideas for Today's Investors* 8 (2025): 0909, <https://doi.org/10.34133/research.0909>.
15. Y. Feng, Y. Yao, S. Wang, et al., "Role of Hetero-Doped Reduced Graphene Oxide in Suppressing Elemental Dissolution in Manganese Selenide Cathode for Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *ChemSusChem* 18, no. 8 (2025): e202402101, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202402101>.
16. S. Chu, Y. Cui, and N. Liu, "The Path Towards Sustainable Energy," *Nature Materials* 16, no. 1 (2017): 16–22, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat4834>.
17. P. E. Brockway, A. Owen, L. I. Brand-Correa, and L. Hardt, "Estimation of Global Final-Stage Energy-Return-On-Investment for Fossil Fuels With Comparison to Renewable Energy Sources," *Nature Energy* 4, no. 7 (2019): 612–621, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-019-0425-z>.
18. M. D. Staples, R. Malina, and S. R. H. Barrett, "The Limits of Bioenergy for Mitigating Global Life-Cycle Greenhouse Gas Emissions From Fossil Fuels," *Nature Energy* 2, no. 2 (2017): 16202, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nenergy.2016.202>.
19. Z. Xu, Y. Yuan, Q. Tang, et al., "Facile Construction of a Multi-layered Interface for a Durable Lithium-Rich Cathode," *Carbon Energy* 5, no. 9 (2023): e332, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cey2.332>.
20. J. Guo, W. Zhai, Q. Sun, et al., "Facilely Tunable Core-Shell Si@SiO_x Nanostructures Prepared in Aqueous Solution for Lithium Ion Battery Anode," *Electrochimica Acta* 342 (2020): 136068, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2020.136068>.
21. Z. Xu, X. Guo, J. Wang, et al., "Restraining the Octahedron Collapse in Lithium and Manganese Rich NCM Cathode Toward Suppressing Structure Transformation," *Advanced Energy Materials* 12, no. 35 (2022): 2201323, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202201323>.
22. M. Tian, Y. Yan, H. Yu, et al., "Designer Lithium Reservoirs for Ultralong Life Lithium Batteries for Grid Storage," *Advances in Materials* 36, no. 25 (2024): 2400707, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202400707>.
23. Q. Sun, J. Li, C. Hao, and L. Ci, "Focusing on the Subsequent Coulombic Efficiencies of SiO_x: Initial High-Temperature Charge After Over-Capacity Prethiation for High-Efficiency SiO_x-Based Full-Cell

- Battery,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 14, no. 12 (2022): 14284–14292, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.2c01392>.
24. N. Nitta, F. Wu, J. T. Lee, and G. Yushin, “Li-ion Battery Materials: Present and Future,” *Materials Today* 18, no. 5 (2015): 252–264, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2014.10.040>.
25. V. Etacheri, R. Marom, R. Elazari, G. Salitra, and D. Aurbach, “Challenges in the Development of Advanced Li-ion Batteries: A Review,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 4, no. 9 (2011): 3243–3262, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1EE01598B>.
26. P. Liu, L. Yang, B. Xiao, et al., “Revealing Lithium Battery Gas Generation for Safer Practical Applications,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 32, no. 47 (2022): 2208586, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202208586>.
27. Z. Xu, L. Ci, Y. Yuan, et al., “Potassium Prussian Blue-Coated Li-Rich Cathode With Enhanced Lithium Ion Storage Property,” *Nano Energy* 75 (2020): 104942, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.104942>.
28. L. Dai, Q. Sun, L. Chen, et al., “Ag Doped Urchin-Like α -MnO₂ Toward Efficient and Bifunctional Electrocatalysts for Li-O₂ Batteries,” *Nano Research* 13, no. 9 (2020): 2356–2364, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-020-2855-0>.
29. D. Zeng, J. Yao, L. Zhang, et al., “Promoting Favorable Interfacial Properties in Lithium-Based Batteries Using chlorine-rich Sulfide Inorganic Solid-State Electrolytes,” *Nature Communications* 13, no. 1 (2022): 1909, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29596-8>.
30. X. Gao, Z. Xing, M. Wang, et al., “Comprehensive Insights Into Solid-State Electrolytes and Electrode-Electrolyte Interfaces in All-Solid-State Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Energy Storage Materials* 60 (2023): 102821, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2023.102821>.
31. J. Wang, Y. Yamada, K. Sodeyama, et al., “Fire-Extinguishing Organic Electrolytes for Safe Batteries,” *Nature Energy* 3, no. 1 (2018): 22–29, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-017-0033-8>.
32. J. Chen, H. Yang, X. Zhang, et al., “Highly Reversible Lithium-Metal Anode and Lithium-Sulfur Batteries Enabled by an Intrinsic Safe Electrolyte,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 11, no. 36 (2019): 33419–33427, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.9b09215>.
33. L. Suo, O. Borodin, T. Gao, et al., ““Water-In-Salt” Electrolyte Enables High-Voltage Aqueous Lithium-ion Chemistries,” *Science* 350, no. 6263 (2015): 938–943, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aab1595>.
34. B. Yang, C. Li, J. Zhou, J. Liu, and Q. Zhang, “Pyrrolidinium-Based Ionic Liquid Electrolyte With Organic Additive and LiTFSI for High-Safety Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Electrochimica Acta* 148 (2014): 39–45, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2014.10.001>.
35. Y. Wang, G. Yang, F. Jiang, et al., “Fabrication of Porous Imidazole Polymerized Ionic Liquids With Fast Ion Diffusing Kinetics for Super Lithiation Anode Materials in Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 10, no. 32 (2022): 16795–16802, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ta04223a>.
36. K. Xu, “Nonaqueous Liquid Electrolytes for Lithium-Based Rechargeable Batteries,” *Chemical Reviews* 104, no. 10 (2004): 4303–4418, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr030203g>.
37. N. Yabuuchi, K. Kubota, M. Dahbi, and S. Komaba, “Research Development on Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Chemical Reviews* 114, no. 23 (2014): 11636–11682, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500192f>.
38. B. Pinnangudi, M. Kuykendal, and S. Bhadra, “4 – Smart Grid Energy Storage,” in *The Power Grid: Smart, Secure, Green and Reliable*, ed. B. W. D’Andrade (Academic Press, 2017), 93–135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805321-8.00004-5>.
39. X. Wu, K. Song, X. Zhang, et al., “Safety Issues in Lithium Ion Batteries: Materials and Cell Design. Review,” *Frontiers in Energy Research* 7 (2019): 65, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2019.00065>.
40. X. Chang, Z. Yang, Y. Liu, et al., “The Guarantee of Large-scale Energy Storage: Non-Flammable Organic Liquid Electrolytes for High-Safety Sodium Ion Batteries,” *Energy Storage Materials* 69 (2024): 103407, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2024.103407>.
41. J. Deng, W. Yang, Y. Zhang, et al., “Combustion Characteristics and Fire Risk Assessment of EC/DMC/EMC Electrolytes for Li-Ion Batteries,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 110 (2025): 115308, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.115308>.
42. Q. Sun, G. Zeng, J. Li, et al., “Is Soft Carbon a More Suitable Match for SiO_x in Li-ion Battery Anodes?,” *Small* 19, no. 37 (2023): 2302644, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202302644>.
43. A. Yoshino, “The Birth of the Lithium-ion Battery,” *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 51, no. 24 (2012): 5798–5800, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201105006>.
44. A. K. Stephan, “The Age of Li-ion Batteries,” *Joule* 3, no. 11 (2019): 2583–2584, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2019.11.004>.
45. J. M. Tarascon and M. Armand, “Issues and Challenges Facing Rechargeable Lithium Batteries,” *Nature* 414, no. 6861 (2001): 359–367, <https://doi.org/10.1038/35104644>.
46. M. Li, J. Lu, Z. Chen, and K. Amine, “30 Years of Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Advances in Materials* 30, no. 33 (2018): 1800561, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201800561>.
47. A. Manthiram, “An Outlook on Lithium Ion Battery Technology,” *ACS Central Science* 3, no. 10 (2017): 1063–1069, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.7b00288>.
48. Q. Sun, J. Li, M. Yang, et al., “Carbon Microstructure Dependent Li-ion Storage Behaviors in SiO_x/C Anodes,” *Small* 19, no. 25 (2023): 2300759, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202300759>.
49. J. Li, J. Guo, Q. Sun, et al., “Potassium Ions Regulated the Disproportionation of Silicon Monoxide Boosting Its Performance for Lithium-ion Battery Anodes,” *Energy & Fuels* 35, no. 19 (2021): 16202–16211, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.1c02922>.
50. M. Navarro-Segarra, O. A. Ibrahim, I. Martin-Fernandez, et al., “Designed-By-Purpose Power Sources: A Cardboard Primary Battery for Smart Packaging,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 17, no. 15 (2024): 5639–5652, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4EE00306C>.
51. P. K. Singh, S. Mallick, G. A. Kaur, S. Balayan, A. Tiwari, and B. John, “Goodenough’s Pioneering Contributions Towards Advancements in Photo-Rechargeable Lithium Batteries,” *Nano Energy* 128 (2024): 109792, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2024.109792>.
52. J. Li, G. Zeng, S. Horta, et al., “Crystallographic Engineering in Micron-Sized SiO_x Anode Material Toward Stable High-Energy-Density Lithium-ion Batteries,” *ACS Nano* 19, no. 16 (2025): 16096–16109, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5c03074>.
53. J. Li, S. Zhang, G. Zeng, et al., “LiF-Induced Formation of Quartz Nanodomains in Micron-Sized SiO_x Anodes for Durable Lithium-ion Batteries,” *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 8, no. 11 (2025): 7753–7761, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.5c01050>.
54. S. Lee and A. Manthiram, “Can Cobalt Be Eliminated From Lithium-ion Batteries?,” *ACS Energy Letters* 7, no. 9 (2022): 3058–3063, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenrgylett.2c01553>.
55. A. Verma, A. J. Henne, D. R. Corbin, and M. B. Shiflett, “Lithium and Cobalt Recovery From LiCoO₂ Using Oxalate Chemistry: Scale-Up and Techno-Economic Analysis,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* 61, no. 15 (2022): 5285–5294, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c04876>.
56. S. Horn, A. G. Gunn, E. Petavratzi, et al., “Cobalt Resources in Europe and the Potential for New Discoveries,” *Ore Geology Reviews* 130 (2021): 103915, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oregeorev.2020.103915>.
57. W. He, D. Yuan, J. Qian, X. Ai, H. Yang, and Y. Cao, “Enhanced high-rate Capability and Cycling Stability of Na-Stabilized Layered Li_{1.2}[Co_{0.13}Ni_{0.13}Mn_{0.54}] O₂ Cathode Material,” *Journal of Materials*

- Chemistry A* 1, no. 37 (2013): 11397–11403, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ta12296d>.
58. Q. Sun, D. Li, J. Cheng, et al., “Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Derived From Pre-oxidized Pitch for Surface Dominated Potassium-Ion Storage,” *Carbon* 155 (2019): 601–610, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2019.08.059>.
59. C. Vaalma, D. Buchholz, M. Weil, and S. Passerini, “A Cost and Resource Analysis of Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Nature Reviews Materials* 3, no. 4 (2018): 18013, <https://doi.org/10.1038/natrevmats.2018.13>.
60. P. Barpanda, G. Oyama, S.-i Nishimura, S.-C. Chung, and A. Yamada, “A 3.8-V Earth-Abundant Sodium Battery Electrode,” *Nature Communications* 5, no. 1 (2014): 4358, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5358>.
61. Y.-K. Sun, “Direction for Commercialization of O3-Type Layered Cathodes for Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *ACS Energy Letters* 5, no. 4 (2020): 1278–1280, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.0c00597>.
62. K. Beltrop, S. Beuker, A. Heckmann, M. Winter, and T. Placke, “Alternative Electrochemical Energy Storage: Potassium-Based Dual-Graphite Batteries,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 10, no. 10 (2017): 2090–2094, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7EE01535F>.
63. L. Zhang, W. Wang, S. Lu, and Y. Xiang, “Carbon Anode Materials: A Detailed Comparison Between Na-ion and K-ion Batteries,” *Advanced Energy Materials* 11, no. 11 (2021): 2003640, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202003640>.
64. Q. Sun, M. Yang, G. Zeng, et al., “Insights into the Potassium Ion Storage Behavior and Phase Evolution of a Tailored Yolk–Shell SnSe@C Anode,” *Small* 18, no. 39 (2022): 2203459, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202203459>.
65. X. Lin, Y. Liu, H. Tan, and B. Zhang, “Advanced Lignin-Derived Hard Carbon for Na-Ion Batteries and a Comparison With Li and K Ion Storage,” *Carbon* 157 (2020): 316–323, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2019.10.045>.
66. J. Hu, H. Wang, S. Wang, et al., “Electrochemical Deposition Mechanism of Sodium and Potassium,” *Energy Storage Materials* 36 (2021): 91–98, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2020.12.017>.
67. Y. Fang, L. Xiao, Z. Chen, X. Ai, Y. Cao, and H. Yang, “Recent Advances in Sodium-Ion Battery Materials,” *Electrochemical Energy Reviews* 1, no. 3 (2018): 294–323, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-018-0008-x>.
68. T. Wang, D. Su, D. Shanmukaraj, T. Rojo, M. Armand, and G. Wang, “Electrode Materials for Sodium-Ion Batteries: Considerations on Crystal Structures and Sodium Storage Mechanisms,” *Electrochemical Energy Reviews* 1, no. 2 (2018): 200–237, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-018-0009-9>.
69. Q. Sun, D. Li, L. Dai, Z. Liang, and L. Ci, “Structural Engineering of SnS₂ Encapsulated in Carbon Nanoboxes for High-Performance Sodium/Potassium-Ion Batteries Anodes,” *Small* 16, no. 45 (2020): 2005023, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202005023>.
70. M. K. Khan, M. Raza, M. Shahbaz, U. Farooq, and M. U. Akram, “Recent Advancement in Energy Storage Technologies and Their Applications,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 92 (2024): 112112, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.112112>.
71. R. Aalund, W. Diao, L. Kong, and M. Pecht, “Understanding the Non-Collision Related Battery Safety Risks in Electric Vehicles a Case Study in Electric Vehicle Recalls and the LG Chem Battery,” *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 89527–89532, <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2021.3090304>.
72. I. Cho, S. Park, and J. Kim, “A Fire Risk Assessment Method for High-Capacity Battery Packs Using Interquartile Range Filter,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 50 (2022): 104663, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.104663>.
73. B. Xu, J. Lee, D. Kwon, L. Kong, and M. Pecht, “Mitigation Strategies for Li-ion Battery Thermal Runaway: A Review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 150 (2021): 111437, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111437>.
74. Y. Wang, X. Feng, W. Huang, X. He, L. Wang, and M. Ouyang, “Challenges and Opportunities to Mitigate the Catastrophic Thermal Runaway of High-Energy Batteries,” *Advanced Energy Materials* 13, no. 15 (2023): 2203841, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202203841>.
75. G. Jiang, J. Liu, Z. Wang, and J. Ma, “Stable Non-Flammable Phosphate Electrolyte for Lithium Metal Batteries via Solvation Regulation by the Additive,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 33, no. 30 (2023): 2300629, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202300629>.
76. T. Doi, R. J. Taccori, R. Fujii, et al., “Non-Flammable and Highly Concentrated Carbonate Ester-Free Electrolyte Solutions for 5 V-Class Positive Electrodes in Lithium-ion Batteries,” *ChemSusChem* 14, no. 11 (2021): 2445–2451, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202100523>.
77. R. Gond, W. van Ekeren, R. Mogensen, A. J. Naylor, and R. Younesi, “Non-Flammable Liquid Electrolytes for Safe Batteries,” *Materials Horizons* 8, no. 11 (2021): 2913–2928, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1mh00748c>.
78. J. Kim, J. Lee, J. You, et al., “Conductive Polymers for Next-Generation Energy Storage Systems: Recent Progress and New Functions,” *Materials Horizons* 3, no. 6 (2016): 517–535, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6mh00165c>.
79. Y. Dai and A. Panahi, “Thermal Runaway Process in Lithium-ion Batteries: A Review,” *Next Energy* 6 (2025): 100186, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nxener.2024.100186>.
80. X. Feng, F. Zhang, W. Huang, Y. Peng, C. Xu, and M. Ouyang, “Mechanism of Internal Thermal Runaway Propagation in Blade Batteries,” *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 89 (2024): 184–194, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2023.09.050>.
81. T. Jia, Y. Zhang, C. Ma, S. Li, H. Yu, and G. Liu, “The Early Warning for Overcharge Thermal Runaway of Lithium-ion Batteries Based on a Composite Parameter,” *Journal of Power Sources* 555 (2023): 232393, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.232393>.
82. J. Wu, S. Weng, X. Zhang, et al., “In Situ Detecting Thermal Stability of Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI),” *Small* 19, no. 25 (2023): 2208239, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202208239>.
83. D. Jie, C. Baohui, L. Jiazheng, Z. Tiannian, and W. Chuanping, “Thermal Runaway and Combustion Characteristics, Risk and Hazard Evaluation of Lithium-Iron Phosphate Battery Under Different Thermal Runaway Triggering Modes,” *Applied Energy* 368 (2024): 123451, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123451>.
84. S. Miao, Y. You, Z. Wang, et al., “Non-Flammable Electrolytes for High-Safety Sodium-ion Batteries,” *Chemical Society Reviews* 54, no. 20 (2025): 9289–9316, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5CS00236B>.
85. J. Xie and Y.-C. Lu, “Designing Nonflammable Liquid Electrolytes for Safe Li-ion Batteries,” *Advances in Materials* 37, no. 2 (2025): 2312451, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202312451>.
86. H. Wang, L. Nie, X. Chu, et al., “Flame-Retardant Nonaqueous Electrolytes for High-Safety Potassium-Ion Batteries,” *Small Methods* 8, no. 7 (2024): 2301104, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202301104>.
87. S. Yang, T. Meng, Z. Wang, and X. Hu, “Unveiling Decaying Mechanism of Non-Flammable All-Fluorinated Carbonate Electrolytes in Lithium Metal Batteries With 4.6-V LiCoO₂ Cathodes at Elevated Temperatures,” *Energy Storage Materials* 65 (2024): 103177, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2024.103177>.
88. M. Klein, M. Binder, M. Koželj, et al., “Understanding the Role of Imide-Based Salts and Borate-Based Additives for Safe and High-Performance Glyoxal-Based Electrolytes in Ni-Rich NMC₈₁₁ Cathodes for Li-ion Batteries,” *Small* 20, no. 42 (2024): 2401610, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202401610>.
89. Q. Huang, S. Lu, X. Liu, K. Zheng, D. Xu, and C. Liu, “Experimental Thermal Hazard Investigation on Carbonate Electrolytes Using a Cone

- Calorimeter,” *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering* 25 (2021): 100912, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2021.100912>.
90. L. Wildersinn, D. Stottmeister, F. Jeschull, A. Groß, and A. Hofmann, “Decomposition of Binary Mixtures of DMC/EC, EMC/EC, and DEC/EC on Potassium Surfaces; GC, XPS, and Calculation,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 17, no. 6 (2025): 10055–10072, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmami.4c17461>.
91. D. Zhu, Y. Ren, Y. Yu, et al., “Flame-Retardant Additive/Co-Solvent Contained in Organic Solution for Safe Second Batteries: A Review,” *Chemelectrochem* 10, no. 8 (2023): e202300009, <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.202300009>.
92. L. Schafzahl, H. Ehmann, M. Kriechbaum, et al., “Long-Chain Li and Na Alkyl Carbonates as Solid Electrolyte Interphase Components: Structure, Ion Transport, and Mechanical Properties,” *Chemistry of Materials* 30, no. 10 (2018): 3338–3345, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.8b00750>.
93. D. Ouyang, K. Wang, J. Guan, and Z. Wang, “Liquid Non-Aqueous Electrolytes for High-Voltage and High-Safety Lithium-ion Cells: A Review,” *Journal of Power Sources* 607 (2024): 234550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2024.234550>.
94. R. Kido, T. Horikawa, A. Sano, et al., “Highly Safe Quasi-Solid-State Lithium Ion Batteries With Two Kinds of Nearly Saturated and Non-Flammable Electrolyte Solutions,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 102 (2024): 114115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.114115>.
95. C. D. Quilty, D. Wu, W. Li, et al., “Electron and Ion Transport in Lithium and Lithium-ion Battery Negative and Positive Composite Electrodes,” *Chemical Reviews* 123, no. 4 (2023): 1327–1363, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00214>.
96. S. K. Sharma, G. Sharma, A. Gaur, et al., “Progress in Electrode and Electrolyte Materials: Path to All-Solid-State Li-ion Batteries,” *Energy Advances* 1, no. 8 (2022): 457–510, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ya00043a>.
97. O. Borodin, X. Ren, J. Vatamanu, A. von Wald Cresce, J. Knap, and K. Xu, “Modeling Insight into Battery Electrolyte Electrochemical Stability and Interfacial Structure,” *Accounts of Chemical Research* 50, no. 12 (2017): 2886–2894, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.accounts.7b00486>.
98. Y.-K. Liu, C.-Z. Zhao, J. Du, X.-Q. Zhang, A.-B. Chen, and Q. Zhang, “Research Progresses of Liquid Electrolytes in Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Small* 19, no. 8 (2023): 2205315, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202205315>.
99. Q.-K. Zhang, X.-Q. Zhang, H. Yuan, and J.-Q. Huang, “Thermally Stable and Nonflammable Electrolytes for Lithium Metal Batteries: Progress and Perspectives,” *Small Science* 1, no. 10 (2021): 2100058, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ssmsc.202100058>.
100. F. Wu, N. Zhu, Y. Bai, L. Liu, H. Zhou, and C. Wu, “Highly Safe Ionic Liquid Electrolytes for Sodium-Ion Battery: Wide Electrochemical Window and Good Thermal Stability,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 8, no. 33 (2016): 21381–21386, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmami.6b07054>.
101. S. Samantaray, D. Mohanty, I. M. Hung, M. Moniruzzaman, and S. K. Satpathy, “Unleashing Recent Electrolyte Materials for Next-Generation Supercapacitor Applications: A Comprehensive Review,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 72 (2023): 108352, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.108352>.
102. L. Xu, J. Li, C. Liu, G. Zou, H. Hou, and X. Ji, “Research Progress in Inorganic Solid-State Electrolytes for Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Acta Physico-Chimica Sinica* 36, no. 5 (2020): 1905013, <https://doi.org/10.3866/PKU.WHXB201905013>.
103. V. Ramar, C. Pszolla, M. Rapp, M. Borck, and L. Zinck, “Non-Flammable Inorganic Liquid Electrolyte Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 167, no. 7 (2020): 070521, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/ab7119>.
104. K. Sirengo, A. Babu, B. Brennan, and S. C. Pillai, “Ionic Liquid Electrolytes for Sodium-Ion Batteries to Control Thermal Runaway,” *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 81 (2023): 321–338, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2023.02.046>.
105. X. Tian, Y. Yi, B. Fang, et al., “Design Strategies of Safe Electrolytes for Preventing Thermal Runaway in Lithium Ion Batteries,” *Chemistry of Materials* 32, no. 23 (2020): 9821–9848, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.0c02428>.
106. N. Takenaka, T. Fujie, A. Bouibes, Y. Yamada, A. Yamada, and M. Nagaoka, “Microscopic Formation Mechanism of Solid Electrolyte Interphase Film in Lithium-Ion Batteries With Highly Concentrated Electrolyte,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 122, no. 5 (2018): 2564–2571, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b11650>.
107. K. Takada, Y. Yamada, and A. Yamada, “Optimized Nonflammable Concentrated Electrolytes by Introducing a Low-Dielectric Diluent,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 11, no. 39 (2019): 35770–35776, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmami.9b12709>.
108. Z. Ye, J. Li, and Z. Li, “Recent Progress in Nonflammable Electrolytes and Cell Design for Safe Li-ion Batteries,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 11, no. 29 (2023): 15576–15599, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ta01951a>.
109. T. Yoon, M. S. Milien, B. S. Parimalam, and B. L. Lucht, “Thermal Decomposition of the Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) on Silicon Electrodes for Lithium Ion Batteries,” *Chemistry of Materials* 29, no. 7 (2017): 3237–3245, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.7b00454>.
110. X. N. Feng, M. G. Ouyang, X. Liu, L. G. Lu, Y. Xia, and X. M. He, “Thermal Runaway Mechanism of Lithium Ion Battery for Electric Vehicles: A Review. Review,” *Energy Storage Materials* 10 (2018): 246–267, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2017.05.013>.
111. X. Feng, D. Ren, X. He, and M. Ouyang, “Mitigating Thermal Runaway of Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Joule* 4, no. 4 (2020): 743–770, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.02.010>.
112. A. Kvasha, C. Gutiérrez, U. Osa, et al., “A Comparative Study of Thermal Runaway of Commercial Lithium Ion Cells,” *Energy* 159 (2018): 547–557, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.06.173>.
113. J. Kim, J. G. Lee, H.-s Kim, et al., “Thermal Degradation of Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) Layers by Phosphorus Pentafluoride (PF₅) Attack,” *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 164, no. 12 (2017): A2418–A2425, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0761712jes>.
114. Y. Li, X. Liu, L. Wang, et al., “Thermal Runaway Mechanism of Lithium-Ion Battery With LiNi_{0.8}Mn_{0.1}Co_{0.1}O₂ Cathode Materials,” *Nano Energy* 85 (2021): 105878, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.105878>.
115. Z. Jia, P. Qin, Z. Li, et al., “Analysis of Gas Release During the Process of Thermal Runaway of lithium-ion Batteries With Three Different Cathode Materials,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 50 (2022): 104302, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.104302>.
116. J. E, H. Xiao, S. Tian, and Y. Huang, “A Comprehensive Review on Thermal Runaway Model of a lithium-ion Battery: Mechanism, Thermal, Mechanical, Propagation, Gas Venting and Combustion,” *Renewable Energy* 229 (2024): 120762, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120762>.
117. Y. Wu, Q. Wu, M. Sun, Z. Zeng, S. Cheng, and J. Xie, “Enhancing Safety in Lithium Batteries: A Review on Functional Separators Controlling Substance and Heat During Thermal Runaway,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 35, no. n/a (2025): 2425698: n/a, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202425698>.
118. W. Li, K. R. Crompton, C. Hacker, and J. K. Ostanek, “Comparison of Current Interrupt Device and Vent Design for 18650 Format Lithium-ion Battery Caps,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 32 (2020): 101890, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101890>.
119. J. Niu, S. Deng, X. Gao, H. Niu, Y. Fang, and Z. Zhang, “Experimental Study on Low Thermal Conductive and Flame Retardant Phase Change Composite Material for Mitigating Battery Thermal Runaway

- Propagation,” *Journal of Energy Storage* 47 (2022): 103557, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2021.103557>.
120. E. Matios, H. Wang, C. Wang, et al., “Graphene Regulated Ceramic Electrolyte for Solid-State Sodium Metal Battery With Superior Electrochemical Stability,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 11, no. 5 (2019): 5064–5072, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b19519>.
121. T. Yamaguchi, H. Yamada, T. Fujiwara, and K. Hori, “Simulations of Dielectric Constants and Viscosities of Organic Electrolytes by Quantum Mechanics and Molecular Dynamics,” *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 312 (2020): 113288, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2020.113288>.
122. D. Hubble, D. E. Brown, Y. Zhao, et al., “Liquid Electrolyte Development for Low-Temperature Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 15, no. 2 (2022): 550–578, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EE01789F>.
123. J. Cao, L. Wang, M. Fang, et al., “Interfacial Compatibility of Gel Polymer Electrolyte and Electrode on Performance of Li-ion Battery,” *Electrochimica Acta* 114 (2013): 527–532, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2013.10.052>.
124. T. Placke, A. Heckmann, R. Schmich, P. Meister, K. Beltróp, and M. Winter, “Perspective on Performance, Cost, and Technical Challenges for Practical Dual-Ion Batteries,” *Joule* 2, no. 12 (2018): 2528–2550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.09.003>.
125. Y. Huang, L. Zhao, L. Li, M. Xie, F. Wu, and R. Chen, “Electrolytes and Electrolyte/Electrode Interfaces in Sodium-Ion Batteries: From Scientific Research to Practical Application,” *Advances in Materials* 31, no. 21 (2019): 1808393, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201808393>.
126. C. Zhong, Y. Deng, W. Hu, J. Qiao, L. Zhang, and J. Zhang, “A Review of Electrolyte Materials and Compositions for Electrochemical Supercapacitors,” *Chemical Society Reviews* 44, no. 21 (2015): 7484–7539, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cs00303b>.
127. M. Li, C. Wang, Z. Chen, K. Xu, and J. Lu, “New Concepts in Electrolytes,” *Chemical Reviews* 120, no. 14 (2020): 6783–6819, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00531>.
128. Q. Wang, L. Jiang, Y. Yu, and J. Sun, “Progress of Enhancing the Safety of Lithium Ion Battery From the Electrolyte Aspect,” *Nano Energy* 55 (2019): 93–114, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.10.035>.
129. V. A. Azov, K. S. Egorova, M. M. Seitkalieva, A. S. Kashin, and V. P. Ananikov, “‘Solvent-In-Salt’ Systems for Design of New Materials in Chemistry, Biology and Energy Research,” *Chemical Society Reviews* 47, no. 4 (2018): 1250–1284, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CS00547D>.
130. Z. Song, X. Wang, W. Feng, M. Armand, Z. Zhou, and H. Zhang, “Designer Anions for Better Rechargeable Lithium Batteries and Beyond,” *Advances in Materials* 36, no. 33 (2024): 2310245, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202310245>.
131. G. G. Eshetu, S. Grugeon, H. Kim, et al., “Comprehensive Insights Into the Reactivity of Electrolytes Based on Sodium Ions,” *ChemSusChem* 9, no. 5 (2016): 462–471, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201501605>.
132. X. Ma, D. Zhang, J. Wen, L. Fan, A. M. Rao, and B. Lu, “Sustainable Electrolytes: Design Principles and Recent Advances,” *Chemistry - A European Journal* 30, no. 36 (2024): e202400332, <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.202400332>.
133. G. Lu, Y. Zhang, J. Zhang, et al., “Trade-Offs Between Ion-Conducting and Mechanical Properties: The Case of Polyacrylate Electrolytes,” *Carbon Energy* 5, no. 2 (2023): e287, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cey2.287>.
134. E. Cho, J. Mun, O. B. Chae, et al., “Corrosion/Passivation of Aluminum Current Collector in Bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide-Based Ionic Liquid for Lithium-ion Batteries. Article,” *Electrochemistry Communications* 22 (2012): 1–3, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2012.05.018>.
135. M. Kerner, N. Plylahan, J. Scheers, and P. Johansson, “Ionic Liquid Based Lithium Battery Electrolytes: Fundamental Benefits of Utilising Both TFSI and FSI Anions?,” *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 17, no. 29 (2015): 19569–19581, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cp01891a>.
136. J.-G. Han, K. Kim, Y. Lee, and N.-S. Choi, “Scavenging Materials to Stabilize LiPF₆-Containing Carbonate-Based Electrolytes for Li-ion Batteries,” *Advances in Materials* 31, no. 20 (2019): 1804822, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201804822>.
137. D. V. Korabel’nikov and Y. N. Zhuravlev, “Effect of Pressure on the Structure and the Electronic Properties of LiClO₄, NaClO₄, KClO₄, and NH₄ClO₄,” *Physics of the Solid State* 59, no. 2 (2017): 254–261, <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1063783417020123>.
138. K. B. Hueso, M. Armand, and T. Rojo, “High Temperature Sodium Batteries: Status, Challenges and Future Trends,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 6, no. 3 (2013): 734–749, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3EE24086J>.
139. Q. Man, C. Wei, K. Tian, et al., “Molecular-Level Design of High Flash Point Solvents Enables High-Safety and Dual-Function Chemical Presodiation of Hard Carbon and Alloy Anodes for High-Performance Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Advanced Energy Materials* 14, no. 24 (2024): 2401016, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202401016>.
140. Y. Sun, P. Shi, H. Xiang, X. Liang, and Y. Yu, “High-Safety Nonaqueous Electrolytes and Interphases for Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Small* 15, no. 14 (2019): e1805479, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201805479>.
141. A. Ponrouch, D. Monti, A. Boschini, B. Steen, P. Johansson, and M. R. Palacin, “Non-Aqueous Electrolytes for Sodium-Ion Batteries,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 3, no. 1 (2015): 22–42, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ta04428b>.
142. C. X. Geng, D. Buchholz, G. T. Kim, et al., “Influence of Salt Concentration on the Properties of Sodium-Based Electrolytes. Article,” *Small Methods* 3, no. 4 (2019): 9–1800208, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.201800208>.
143. L. Otaegui, E. Goikolea, F. Aguesse, M. Armand, T. Rojo, and G. Singh, “Effect of the Electrolytic Solvent and Temperature on Aluminium Current Collector Stability: A Case of Sodium-Ion Battery Cathode,” *Journal of Power Sources* 297 (2015): 168–173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.07.084>.
144. M. Zhou, P. Bai, X. Ji, J. Yang, C. Wang, and Y. Xu, “Electrolytes and Interphases in Potassium Ion Batteries,” *Advances in Materials* 33, no. 7 (2021): 2003741, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202003741>.
145. Y. Xu, T. Ding, D. Sun, X. Ji, and X. Zhou, “Recent Advances in Electrolytes for Potassium-Ion Batteries,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 33, no. 6 (2023): 2211290, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202211290>.
146. W. Wang, C. Liao, L. Liu, et al., “Comparable Investigation of Tervalent and Pentavalent Phosphorus Based Flame Retardants on Improving the Safety and Capacity of Lithium-ion Batteries,” *Journal of Power Sources* 420 (2019): 143–151, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.02.037>.
147. J.-H. Kim, J.-H. Hyun, S. Kim, W. H. Park, and S.-H. Yu, “Phosphorus-Based Flame-Retardant Electrolytes for Lithium Batteries,” *Advanced Energy Materials* 15, no. 23 (2025): 2500587, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202500587>.
148. H. Cheng, Z. Ma, P. Kumar, et al., “Non-Flammable Electrolyte Mediated by Solvation Chemistry Toward High-Voltage Lithium-Ion Batteries,” *ACS Energy Letters* 9, no. 4 (2024): 1604–1616, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.3c02789>.
149. Z. Zeng, B. Wu, L. Xiao, et al., “Safer Lithium Ion Batteries Based on Nonflammable Electrolyte,” *Journal of Power Sources* 279 (2015): 6–12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.12.150>.
150. Z. Zeng, X. Jiang, R. Li, et al., “A Safer Sodium-Ion Battery Based on Nonflammable Organic Phosphate Electrolyte,” *Advanced Science* 3, no. 9 (2016): 1600066, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.201600066>.

151. R. Fu, B. Zhang, T. Lu, et al., "A Dilute and Non-Flammable Electrolyte Engineering Enables Stable SEI for Low-Temperature Zinc Batteries," *Energy Storage Materials* 80 (2025): 104374, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2025.104374>.
152. H. V. T. Nguyen, J. Kim, and K.-K. Lee, "High-Voltage and Intrinsically Safe Supercapacitors Based on a Trimethyl Phosphate Electrolyte," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 9, no. 36 (2021): 20725–20736, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ta05584d>.
153. X. Wang, E. Yasukawa, and S. Kasuya, "Nonflammable Trimethyl Phosphate Solvent-Containing Electrolytes for Lithium-ion Batteries: I. Fundamental Properties," *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 148, no. 10 (2001): A1058, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1397773>.
154. Q. Zheng, Y. Yamada, R. Shang, et al., "A Cyclic Phosphate-based Battery Electrolyte for High Voltage and Safe Operation," *Nature Energy* 5, no. 4 (2020): 291–298, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0567-z>.
155. N. von Aspern, S. Röser, B. Rezaei Rad, et al., "Phosphorus Additives for Improving High Voltage Stability and Safety of Lithium Ion Batteries," *Journal of Fluorine Chemistry* 198 (2017): 24–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluchem.2017.02.005>.
156. H. Nakagawa, M. Ochida, Y. Domi, et al., "Electrochemical Raman Study of Edge Plane Graphite Negative-Electrodes in Electrolytes Containing Trialkyl Phosphoric Ester," *Journal of Power Sources* 212 (2012): 148–153, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2012.04.013>.
157. J. Feng, P. Ma, H. Yang, and L. Lu, "Understanding the Interactions of Phosphonate-Based Flame-Retarding Additives With Graphitic Anode for Lithium Ion Batteries," *Electrochimica Acta* 114 (2013): 688–692, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2013.10.104>.
158. Z. Zeng, V. Murugesan, K. S. Han, et al., "Non-Flammable Electrolytes With High Salt-To-Solvent Ratios for Li-ion and Li-metal Batteries," *Nature Energy* 3, no. 8 (2018): 674–681, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0196-y>.
159. Q. Li, X. Liu, X. Han, et al., "Identification of the Solid Electrolyte Interface on the Si/C Composite Anode With FEC as the Additive," *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 11, no. 15 (2019): 14066–14075, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b22221>.
160. D. A. Conner, D. T. Welna, Y. Chang, and H. R. Allcock, "Influence of Terminal Phenyl Groups on the Side Chains of Phosphazene Polymers: Structure–Property Relationships and Polymer Electrolyte Behavior," *Macromolecules* 40, no. 2 (2007): 322–328, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma061916e>.
161. Y. Lai, C. Ren, H. Lu, Z. Zhang, and J. Li, "Compatibility of Diphenyloctyl Phosphate as Flame-Retardant Additive With $\text{LiNi}_{1/3}\text{Co}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$ /Artificial Graphite Cells," *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 159, no. 8 (2012): A1267–A1272, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.058208jes>.
162. X. L. Yao, S. Xie, C. H. Chen, et al., "Comparative Study of Trimethyl Phosphite and Trimethyl Phosphate as Electrolyte Additives in Lithium Ion Batteries," *Journal of Power Sources* 144, no. 1 (2005): 170–175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2004.11.042>.
163. Z. Zhou, Y. Ma, L. Wang, et al., "Triphenyl Phosphite as an Electrolyte Additive to Improve the Cyclic Stability of Lithium-Rich Layered Oxide Cathode for Lithium-ion Batteries," *Electrochimica Acta* 216 (2016): 44–50, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2016.09.008>.
164. K. Matsumoto, K. Inoue, and K. Utsugi, "A Highly Safe Battery With a Non-Flammable Triethyl-Phosphate-Based Electrolyte," *Journal of Power Sources* 273 (2015): 954–958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.09.086>.
165. Z. Deng, Y. Jia, Y. Deng, et al., "Coordination Structure Regulation in Non-Flammable Electrolyte Enabling High Voltage Lithium Electrochemistry," *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 96 (2024): 282–290, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2024.04.041>.
166. C. Liao, L. Han, W. Wang, et al., "Non-Flammable Electrolyte With Lithium Nitrate as the Only Lithium Salt for Boosting Ultra-Stable Cycling and Fire-Safety Lithium Metal Batteries," *Advanced Functional Materials* 33, no. 17 (2023): 2212605, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202212605>.
167. N. D. Nam, I. J. Park, and J. G. Kim, "Triethyl and Tributyl Phosphite as Flame-Retarding Additives in Li-ion Batteries," *Metals and Materials International* 18, no. 1 (2012): 189–196, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12540-012-0025-y>.
168. S. S. Zhang, K. Xu, and T. R. Jow, "Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) Phosphite as a Co-Solvent for Nonflammable Electrolytes in Li-ion Batteries," *Journal of Power Sources* 113, no. 1 (2003): 166–172, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-7753\(02\)00537-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-7753(02)00537-2).
169. J. Wang, F. Lin, H. Jia, J. Yang, C. W. Monroe, and Y. NuLi, "Towards a Safe Lithium–Sulfur Battery With a Flame-Inhibiting Electrolyte and a Sulfur-Based Composite Cathode," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 53, no. 38 (2014): 10099–10104, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201405157>.
170. S. Izquierdo-Gonzales, W. Li, and B. L. Lucht, "Hexamethylphosphoramide as a Flame Retarding Additive for lithium-ion Battery Electrolytes," *Journal of Power Sources* 135, no. 1 (2004): 291–296, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2004.04.011>.
171. S.-J. Tan, Y.-F. Tian, Y. Zhao, et al., "Noncoordinating Flame-Retardant Functional Electrolyte Solvents for Rechargeable Lithium-ion Batteries," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 144, no. 40 (2022): 18240–18245, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.2c08396>.
172. W. Zhang, X. Feng, W. Huang, et al., "Thermal Runaway Inhibition of Lithium-ion Batteries Employing Thermal-Driven Phosphazene Based Electrolytes," *Advanced Functional Materials* n/a, no. n/a (2025): 2508688, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202508688>.
173. S. Sayah, M. Baazizi, M. Karbak, J. Jacquemin, and F. Ghamouss, "Deep and Comprehensive Study on the Impact of Different Phosphazene-Based Flame-Retardant Additives on Electrolyte Properties, Performance, and Durability of High-Voltage LMNO-Based Lithium-ion Batteries," *Energy Technology* 11, no. 11 (2023): 2201446, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202201446>.
174. S. Sayah, I. Douihri, M. Karbak, et al., "Exploring the Formulation and Efficacy of Phosphazene-Based Flame Retardants for Conventional Supercapacitor Electrolytes," *ChemPhysChem* 26, no. 5 (2025): e202400871, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.202400871>.
175. Z. Gao, S. Rao, T. Zhang, et al., "Design Strategies of Flame-Retardant Additives for Lithium Ion Electrolyte," *Journal of Electrochemical Energy Conversion and Storage* 19, no. 3 (2022): 030910, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4053968>.
176. H. Yang, W. Tian, X. Chen, et al., "Flame-Retardant Polymer Electrolyte for Sodium-Ion Batteries," *Batteries & Supercaps* 8, no. 2 (2025): e202400383, <https://doi.org/10.1002/batt.202400383>.
177. A. Swiderska-Mocek, P. Jakobczyk, E. Rudnicka, and A. Lewandowski, "Flammability Parameters of Lithium-ion Battery Electrolytes," *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 318 (2020): 113986, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2020.113986>.
178. Y. Zou, Z. Ma, G. Liu, et al., "Non-Flammable Electrolyte Enables High-Voltage and Wide-Temperature Lithium-ion Batteries With Fast Charging," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 62, no. 8 (2023): e202216189, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202216189>.
179. Y. Wang, X. Yang, Y. Meng, et al., "Fluorine Chemistry in Rechargeable Batteries: Challenges, Progress, and Perspectives," *Chemical Reviews* 124, no. 6 (2024): 3494–3589, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.3c00826>.
180. J. Zhao, L. Liao, F. Shi, et al., "Surface Fluorination of Reactive Battery Anode Materials for Enhanced Stability," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 139, no. 33 (2017): 11550–11558, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.7b05251>.

181. P. Xiao, Y. Zhao, Z. Piao, B. Li, G. Zhou, and H.-M. Cheng, "A Nonflammable Electrolyte for Ultrahigh-Voltage (4.8 V-Class) Lill NCM811 Cells With a Wide Temperature Range of 100°C," *Energy & Environmental Science* 15, no. 6 (2022): 2435–2444, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EE02959B>.
182. S. Zhang, S. Li, X. Wang, et al., "Nonflammable Electrolyte With Low Exothermic Design for Safer Lithium-Based Batteries," *Nano Energy* 114 (2023): 108639, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2023.108639>.
183. S. Lin, H. Hua, Z. Li, and J. Zhao, "Functional Localized High-Concentration Ether-Based Electrolyte for Stabilizing High-Voltage Lithium-Metal Battery," *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 12, no. 30 (2020): 33710–33718, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c07904>.
184. M. C. Smart, B. V. Ratnakumar, V. S. Ryan-Mowrey, et al., "Improved Performance of Lithium-ion Cells With the Use of Fluorinated Carbonate-Based Electrolytes," *Journal of Power Sources* 119 (2003): 359–367, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-7753\(03\)00266-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-7753(03)00266-0).
185. L. Tan, S. Chen, Y. Chen, et al., "Intrinsic Nonflammable Ether Electrolytes for Ultrahigh-Voltage Lithium Metal Batteries Enabled by Chlorine Functionality," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 61, no. 32 (2022): e202203693, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202203693>.
186. C. Zuo, D. Dong, H. Wang, Y. Sun, and Y.-C. Lu, "Bromide-Based Nonflammable Electrolyte for Safe and Long-Life Sodium Metal Batteries," *Energy & Environmental Science* 17, no. 2 (2024): 791–799, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EE03332E>.
187. S. Hegde, V. Ravindrachary, G. Sanjeev, and Ismayil, "Characterization and Charge Transport Properties of Sodium Ion Conducting PEO: Nabr Solid Polymer Electrolyte Films," *Polymer Engineering & Science* 63, no. 8 (2023): 2468–2483, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.26389>.
188. Y.-J. Xu, K.-T. Zhang, J.-R. Wang, and Y.-Z. Wang, "Biopolymer-Based Flame Retardants and Flame-Retardant Materials," *Advances in Materials* 37, no. 22 (2025): 2414880, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202414880>.
189. T. D. Pham, A. Bin Faheem, J. Kim, K. Kwak, and K.-K. Lee, "Non-Flammable Electrolytes Based on a Fluorine-Free Salt for Safe and High-Voltage Lithium Metal Batteries," *Electrochimica Acta* 458 (2023): 142496, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2023.142496>.
190. Z.-H. Wu, Y. Wu, Y. Tang, J.-C. Jiang, and A.-C. Huang, "Evaluation of Composite Flame-Retardant Electrolyte Additives Improvement on the Safety Performance of Lithium-ion Batteries," *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 169 (2023): 285–292, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2022.11.035>.
191. A. Yusuf, Z. Li, X. Yuan, and D.-Y. Wang, "Toward a New Generation of Fire-Safe Energy Storage Devices: Recent Progress on Fire-Retardant Materials and Strategies for Energy Storage Devices," *Small Methods* 6, no. 3 (2022): 2101428, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202101428>.
192. C. F. J. Francis, I. L. Kyratzis, and A. S. Best, "Lithium-ion Battery Separators for Ionic-Liquid Electrolytes: A Review," *Advances in Materials* 32, no. 18 (2020): 1904205, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201904205>.
193. R. Hayes, G. G. Warr, and R. Atkin, "Structure and Nanostructure in Ionic Liquids," *Chemical Reviews* 115, no. 13 (2015): 6357–6426, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500411q>.
194. A. Ghorai, A. Alex, S. P. Balmuchu, S. Banerjee, and S. Choudhury, "Polymer-Based Ionic Liquids in Lithium Batteries," *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* 50 (2025): 101639, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coelec.2024.101639>.
195. A. Shakeel, H. Mahmood, U. Farooq, et al., "Rheology of Pure Ionic Liquids and Their Complex Fluids: A Review," *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 7, no. 16 (2019): 13586–13626, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.9b02232>.
196. T. Zhou, C. Gui, L. Sun, et al., "Energy Applications of Ionic Liquids: Recent Developments and Future Prospects," *Chemical Reviews* 123, no. 21 (2023): 12170–12253, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.3c00391>.
197. R. L. Gardas, H. F. Costa, M. G. Freire, et al., "Densities and Derived Thermodynamic Properties of Imidazolium-Pyridinium-Pyrrolidinium-and Piperidinium-Based Ionic Liquids," *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* 53, no. 3 (2008): 805–811, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jc700670k>.
198. X. Tian, Y. Liu, C. Zhao, et al., "A Shear-Thickening Fluid Based on Ionic Liquid as Dual-Safe Electrolyte for Lithium Batteries," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 503 (2025): 158145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.158145>.
199. A. Santiago-Alonso, J. M. Sánchez-Pico, R. S. Emeterio, M. Villanueva, J. Salgado, and J. J. Parajó, "Pyrrolidinium-Based Ionic Liquids as Advanced Non-Aqueous Electrolytes for Safer Next Generation Lithium Batteries," *Batteries* 10, no. 9 (2024): 319, <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10090319>.
200. J. B. Haskins, W. R. Bennett, J. J. Wu, et al., "Computational and Experimental Investigation of Li-Doped Ionic Liquid Electrolytes: [pyr14][TFSI], [pyr13][FSI], and [EMIM][BF₄]," *Journal of Physical Chemistry B* 118, no. 38 (2014): 11295–11309, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp5061705>.
201. K. Matuszek, S. L. Piper, A. Brzeczek-Szafran, et al., "Unexpected Energy Applications of Ionic Liquids," *Advanced Materials* 36, no. 23 (2024): 2313023, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202313023>.
202. Y. Lu, X. Hou, L. Miao, et al., "Cyclohexanehexone With Ultrahigh Capacity as Cathode Materials for Lithium-ion Batteries," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 58, no. 21 (2019): 7020–7024, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201902185>.
203. K. Xue, Y. Zhao, P.-K. Lee, and D. Y. W. Yu, "Poly(Ionic Liquid) as an Anion Exchange Membrane for a 3.3 V Copper-Lithium Battery," *Energy & Environmental Materials* 6, no. 4 (2023): e12395, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eem2.12395>.
204. F. Ma, Z. Zhang, W. Yan, et al., "Solid Polymer Electrolyte Based on Polymerized Ionic Liquid for High Performance All-Solid-State Lithium-ion Batteries," *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 7, no. 5 (2019): 4675–4683, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.8b04076>.
205. O. Russina, B. Fazio, G. Di Marco, R. Caminiti, and A. Triolo, "Structural Organization in Neat Ionic Liquids and in Their Mixtures," in *The Structure of Ionic Liquids*, ed. R. Caminiti and L. Gontrani (Springer International Publishing, 2014), 39–61, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-01698-6_2.
206. H. F. Xiang, B. Yin, H. Wang, et al., "Improving Electrochemical Properties of Room Temperature Ionic Liquid (RTIL) Based Electrolyte for Li-ion Batteries," *Electrochimica Acta* 55, no. 18 (2010): 5204–5209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2010.04.041>.
207. T. R. C. Shivani, A. Thakur, A. Sharma, and R. Sharma, "Unravelling the Prospects of Electrolytes Containing Ionic Liquids and Deep Eutectic Solvents for Next Generation Lithium Batteries," *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 105 (2025): 482–500, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2025.01.060>.
208. T. Yamamoto, K. Matsumoto, R. Hagiwara, and T. Nohira, "Physicochemical and Electrochemical Properties of K[N(SO₂F)₂]-[N-Methyl-N-propylpyrrolidinium][N(SO₂F)₂] Ionic Liquids for Potassium-Ion Batteries," *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 121, no. 34 (2017): 18450–18458, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b06523>.
209. K. Yoshii, T. Masese, M. Kato, K. Kubota, H. Senoh, and M. Shikano, "Sulfonylamide-Based Ionic Liquids for High-Voltage Potassium-Ion Batteries With Honeycomb Layered Cathode Oxides," *Chemelectrochem* 6, no. 15 (2019): 3901–3910, <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.201900689>.
210. M. Armand, F. Endres, D. R. MacFarlane, H. Ohno, and B. Scrosati, "Ionic-Liquid Materials for the Electrochemical Challenges of the Future," *Nature Materials* 8, no. 8 (2009): 621–629, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat2448>.

211. D. Mecerreyes, "Polymeric Ionic Liquids: Broadening the Properties and Applications of Polyelectrolytes," *Progress in Polymer Science* 36, no. 12 (2011): 1629–1648, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2011.05.007>.
212. P. Mohapatra and A. K. Barick, "Ionic Liquids Based Polymer Electrolytes for Supercapacitor Applications," *Journal of Power Sources* 626 (2025): 235749, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2024.235749>.
213. K. Mishra, N. Devi, S. S. Siwal, et al., "Ionic Liquid-Based Polymer Nanocomposites for Sensors, Energy, Biomedicine, and Environmental Applications: Roadmap to the Future," *Advanced Science* 9, no. 26 (2022): 2202187, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202202187>.
214. S. Mogurampelly and V. Ganesan, "Ion Transport in Polymerized Ionic Liquid-Ionic Liquid Blends," *Macromolecules* 51, no. 23 (2018): 9471–9483, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.8b01460>.
215. B. Li, S. Zhao, J. Zhu, et al., "Rational Polymer Design of Stretchable Poly(Ionic Liquid) Membranes for Dual Applications," *Macromolecules* 54, no. 2 (2021): 896–905, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.0c02335>.
216. X. Zhu, Z. Fang, Q. Deng, et al., "Poly(ionic Liquid)@Pegma Block Polymer Initiated Microphase Separation Architecture in Poly(Ethylene oxide)-Based Solid-State Polymer Electrolyte for Flexible and Self-Healing Lithium Batteries," *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 10, no. 13 (2022): 4173–4185, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c08306>.
217. H. Zhang, X. Liu, H. Li, I. Hasa, and S. Passerini, "Challenges and Strategies for High-Energy Aqueous Electrolyte Rechargeable Batteries," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 60, no. 2 (2021): 598–616, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202004433>.
218. M. Li, X. Wang, J. Meng, et al., "Comprehensive Understandings of Hydrogen Bond Chemistry in Aqueous Batteries," *Advanced Materials* 36, no. 3 (2024): 2308628, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202308628>.
219. G. Zeng, Q. Sun, S. Horta, et al., "A Layered Bi₂Te₃@PPy Cathode for Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries: Mechanism and Application in Printed Flexible Batteries," *Advances in Materials* 36, no. 1 (2024): 2305128, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202305128>.
220. S. Wang, G. Zeng, Q. Sun, et al., "Flexible Electronic Systems via Electrohydrodynamic Jet Printing: A Mnse@Rgo Cathode for Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *ACS Nano* 17, no. 14 (2023): 13256–13268, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.3c00672>.
221. X. Dong, A. Liu, C. Peng, and Y. Huang, "MXenes for the Zinc Anode Protection of Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *Electron* 3, no. 1 (2025): e44, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elt2.44>.
222. C. Liu, Y. Zhu, S. Di, et al., "Crystallinity Engineering of Carbon Nitride Protective Coating for Ultra-Stable Zn Metal Anodes," *Electron* 2, no. 1 (2024): e29, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elt2.29>.
223. Y. Meng, L. Zhang, M. Peng, et al., "Developing Thermoregulatory Hydrogel Electrolyte to Overcome Thermal Runaway in Zinc-Ion Batteries," *Advanced Functional Materials* 32, no. 46 (2022): 2206653, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202206653>.
224. G. Zeng, S. Horta, Q. Sun, et al., "Crystal Growth Engineering for Dendrite-Free Zinc Metal Plating," *Advances in Materials*, (2025): e10906, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202510906>.
225. M. Yu, C. Cao, Z. Sa, et al., "Liquid Metal Alchemy: Unlocking self-healing Gallium-Based Materials for Next-Generation Electronics," *Materials Science and Engineering: R: Reports* 166 (2025): 101073, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mserr.2025.101073>.
226. J. Xu and C. Wang, "Perspective—Electrolyte Design for Aqueous Batteries: From Ultra-High Concentration to Low Concentration?," *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 169, no. 3 (2022): 030530, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/ac5ba9>.
227. X. Yuan, C.-W. Su, M. Umar, X. Shao, and O.-R. LobonT, "The Race to Zero Emissions: Can Renewable Energy be the Path to Carbon Neutrality?," *Journal of Environmental Management* 308 (2022): 114648, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114648>.
228. W. Li, J. R. Dahn, and D. S. Wainwright, "Rechargeable Lithium Batteries With Aqueous Electrolytes," *Science* 264, no. 5162 (1994): 1115–1118, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.264.5162.1115>.
229. S. Chen, M. Zhang, P. Zou, B. Sun, and S. Tao, "Historical Development and Novel Concepts on Electrolytes for Aqueous Rechargeable Batteries," *Energy & Environmental Science* 15, no. 5 (2022): 1805–1839, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2EE00004K>.
230. L. Chen, G. Zeng, Q. Sun, et al., "K-Ion Preintercalated MnO₂ Nanorods as a High-Rate Cathode Material for Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *Ceramics International* 50, no. 23, Part C (2024): 52103–52109, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.04.324>.
231. G. Zeng, Q. Sun, S. Horta, et al., "Modulating the Solvation Structure to Enhance Amorphous Solid Electrolyte Interface Formation for Ultra-Stable Aqueous Zinc Anode," *Energy & Environmental Science* 18, no. 4 (2025): 1683–1695, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4EE03750B>.
232. H. Wu, J. Hao, Y. Jiang, et al., "Alkaline-Based Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries for Large-Scale Energy Storage," *Nature Communications* 15, no. 1 (2024): 575, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-44855-6>.
233. Z. Lv, Y. Kang, R. Tang, et al., "Stabilizing Layered Superlattice MoSe₂ Anodes by the Rational Solvation Structure Design for Low-Temperature Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *Electron* 1, no. 1 (2023): e5, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elt2.5>.
234. H. Wang, C. Hu, Z. Yang, et al., "A Common Polar Dye Additive as Corrosion Inhibitor and Leveling Agent for Stable Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries," *Electron* 2, no. 1 (2024): e21, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elt2.21>.
235. Y. Yamada, K. Usui, K. Sodeyama, S. Ko, Y. Tateyama, and A. Yamada, "Hydrate-Melt Electrolytes for High-Energy-Density Aqueous Batteries," *Nature Energy* 1, no. 10 (2016): 16129, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nenergy.2016.129>.
236. J. Xie, Z. Liang, and Y.-C. Lu, "Molecular Crowding Electrolytes for High-Voltage Aqueous Batteries," *Nature Materials* 19, no. 9 (2020): 1006–1011, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-020-0667-y>.
237. D. Dong, C.-X. Zhao, X. Zhang, and C. Wang, "Aqueous Electrolytes: From Salt in Water to Water in Salt and Beyond," *Advances in Materials*, no. n/a (2025): 2418700, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202418700>.
238. M. Zhou, Z. Bo, and K. Ostrikov, "Challenges and Prospects of High-Voltage Aqueous Electrolytes for Energy Storage Applications," *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 24, no. 35 (2022): 20674–20688, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2cp02795j>.
239. M. Xia, J. Zhou, and B. Lu, "Comprehensive Insights Into Aqueous Potassium-Ion Batteries," *Advanced Energy Materials* 15, no. 12 (2025): 2404032, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202404032>.
240. H. Bi, X. Wang, H. Liu, et al., "A Universal Approach to Aqueous Energy Storage via Ultralow-Cost Electrolyte With Super-Concentrated Sugar as Hydrogen-Bond-Regulated Solute," *Advanced Materials* 32, no. 16 (2020): 2000074, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202000074>.
241. T. Fukushima, S. Yoshimitsu, and K. Murakoshi, "Inherent Promotion of Ionic Conductivity via Collective Vibrational Strong Coupling of Water With the Vacuum Electromagnetic Field," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 144, no. 27 (2022): 12177–12183, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.2c02991>.
242. D. P. Leonard, Z. Wei, G. Chen, F. Du, and X. Ji, "Water-In-Salt Electrolyte for Potassium-Ion Batteries," *ACS Energy Letters* 3, no. 2 (2018): 373–374, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenrgylett.8b00009>.
243. R.-S. Kuhnelt, D. Reber, and C. Battaglia, "A High-Voltage Aqueous Electrolyte for Sodium-Ion Batteries," *ACS Energy Letters* 2, no. 9 (2017): 2005–2006, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenrgylett.7b00623>.

244. J. L. Liu, C. H. Xu, Z. Chen, S. B. Ni, and Z. X. Shen, "Progress in Aqueous Rechargeable Batteries. Review," *Green Energy & Environment* 3, no. 1 (2018): 20–41, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gee.2017.10.001>.
245. J. Janek and W. G. Zeier, "Challenges in Speeding Up Solid-State Battery Development," *Nature Energy* 8, no. 3 (2023): 230–240, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01208-9>.
246. A. Machín, C. Morant, and F. Márquez, "Advancements and Challenges in Solid-State Battery Technology: An In-Depth Review of Solid Electrolytes and Anode Innovations," *Batteries* 10, no. 1 (2024): 29, <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10010029>.
247. S. Zhao, H. Che, S. Chen, et al., "Research Progress on the Solid Electrolyte of Solid-State Sodium-Ion Batteries," *Electrochemical Energy Reviews* 7, no. 1 (2024): 3, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-023-00196-4>.
248. F. Fu, Y. Zheng, N. Jiang, et al., "A Dual-Salt PEO-Based Polymer Electrolyte With Cross-Linked Polymer Network for High-Voltage Lithium Metal Batteries," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 450 (2022): 137776, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.137776>.
249. X. Wang, C. Zhang, M. Sawczyk, et al., "Ultra-Stable All-Solid-State Sodium Metal Batteries Enabled by Perfluoropolyether-Based Electrolytes," *Nature Materials* 21, no. 9 (2022): 1057–1065, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-022-01296-0>.
250. J. Wen, Q. Zhao, X. Jiang, et al., "Graphene Oxide Enabled Flexible PEO-Based Solid Polymer Electrolyte for All-Solid-State Lithium Metal Battery," *ACS Applied Energy Materials* 4, no. 4 (2021): 3660–3669, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.1c00090>.
251. K. West, B. Zachau-Christiansen, T. Jacobsen, and S. Atlung, "A Rechargeable All-Solid-State Sodium Cell With Polymer Electrolyte," *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 132, no. 12 (1985): 3061–3062, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2113725>.
252. S. Zhang, Q. Sun, G. Hou, et al., "Boosting Fast Interfacial Li⁺ Transport in Solid-State Li Metal Batteries via Ultrathin Al Buffer Layer," *Nano Research* 16, no. 5 (2023): 6825–6832, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-022-5345-8>.
253. S. Yuan, Y. Luo, K. Xia, et al., "Developing Flexible and Safety-Reinforced 3D Polymer Electrolytes Based on Polyethylene Oxide for Solid-State Lithium Metal Batteries," *Journal of Energy Storage* 78 (2024): 109853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.109853>.
254. Q. Liu, T. Yu, H. Yang, et al., "Ion Coordination to Improve Ionic Conductivity in Polymer Electrolytes for High Performance Solid-State Batteries," *Nano Energy* 103 (2022): 107763, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.107763>.
255. A. R. Polu, K. Kim, A. A. Kareem, et al., "Impact of Tetracyanoethylene Plasticizer on PEO Based Solid Polymer Electrolytes for Improved Ionic Conductivity and Solid-State Lithium-ion Battery Performance," *Journal of Power Sources* 625 (2025): 235742, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2024.235742>.
256. S. Das and A. Ghosh, "Effect of Plasticizers on Ionic Conductivity and Dielectric Relaxation of PEO-LiClO₄ Polymer Electrolyte," *Electrochimica Acta* 171 (2015): 59–65, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.04.178>.
257. B. W. Zewde, L. Carbone, S. Greenbaum, and J. Hassoun, "A Novel Polymer Electrolyte Membrane for Application in Solid State Lithium Metal Battery," *Solid State Ionics* 317 (2018): 97–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2017.12.039>.
258. X. Wang, H. Hua, X. Xie, P. Zhang, and J. Zhao, "Hydroxyl on the Filler Surface Promotes Li⁺ Conduction in PEO All-Solid-State Electrolyte," *Solid State Ionics* 372 (2021): 115768, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2021.115768>.
259. M. R. Bonilla, F. A. García Daza, P. Ranque, F. Aguesse, J. Carrasco, and E. Akhmatkaya, "Unveiling Interfacial Li-ion Dynamics in Li₇La₃Zr₂O₁₂/PEO(LiTFSI) Composite Polymer-Ceramic Solid Electrolytes for All-Solid-State Lithium Batteries," *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 13, no. 26 (2021): 30653–30667, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.1c07029>.
260. B. Ramkumar, V. Aravindan, H. Ramasamy, et al., "Ternary Metal Oxide Filled PEO-Based Polymer Electrolyte for Solid-State Lithium Metal Battery: The Role of Filler Particle Size," *Solid State Sciences* 132 (2022): 106958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solidstatesciences.2022.106958>.
261. G. Feuillade and P. Perche, "Ion-Conductive Macromolecular Gels and Membranes for Solid Lithium Cells," *Journal of Applied Electrochemistry* 5, no. 1 (1975): 63–69, <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00625960>.
262. S. Zhang, Q. Sun, P. R. Martínez-Alanis, et al., "Towards Flame Retardant High-Performance Solid-State Lithium Metal Batteries: Poly (Ionic Liquid)-Based Lithiophilic Ion-Conductive Interfaces and Humidity Tolerant Binders," *Nano Energy* 133 (2025): 110424, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2024.110424>.
263. Q. Zhang, F. Liang, Y. Yao, W. Ma, B. Yang, and Y. Dai, "Sodium-Based Solid-State Electrolyte and Its Applications in Energy," *Progress in Chemistry* 31, no. 1 (2019): 210–222, <https://doi.org/10.7536/PC180434>.
264. Q. Ma, Y. Hu, H. Li, L. Chen, X. Huang, and Z. Zhou, "An Sodium Bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)Imide-Based Polymer Electrolyte for Solid-State Sodium Batteries," *Acta Physico-Chimica Sinica* 34, no. 2 (2018): 213–218, https://hero.epa.gov/hero/index.cfm/reference/details/reference_id/4581489.
265. Q. Sun, G. Zeng, X. Xu, et al., "Are Sulfide-Based Solid-State Electrolytes the Best Pair for Si Anodes in Li-ion Batteries?," *Advanced Energy Materials* 14, no. 40 (2024): 2402048, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202402048>.
266. B. Zahiri, A. Patra, C. Kiggins, et al., "Revealing the Role of the Cathode-Electrolyte Interface on Solid-State Batteries," *Nature Materials* 20, no. 10 (2021): 1392–1400, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-021-01016-0>.
267. H. Huo, K. Huang, W. Luo, et al., "Evaluating Interfacial Stability in Solid-State Pouch Cells via Ultrasonic Imaging," *ACS Energy Letters* 7, no. 2 (2022): 650–658, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.1c02363>.
268. T.-T. Zuo, R. Rueß, R. Pan, et al., "A Mechanistic Investigation of the Li₁₀GeP₂S₁₂/LiNi_{1-x-y}Co_xMn_yO₂ Interface Stability in All-Solid-State Lithium Batteries," *Nature Communications* 12, no. 1 (2021): 6669, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26895-4>.
269. D. Li, D. Yu, G. Zhang, et al., "High Configuration Entropy Promises Electrochemical Stability of Chloride Electrolytes for High-Energy, Long-Life All-Solid-State Batteries," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 64, no. 7 (2025): e202419735, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202419735>.
270. T. Famprakis, P. Canepa, J. A. Dawson, M. S. Islam, and C. Masquelier, "Fundamentals of Inorganic Solid-State Electrolytes for Batteries," *Nature Materials* 18, no. 12 (2019): 1278–1291, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-019-0431-3>.
271. Q. Wang, Z. Jiang, C. Yu, L. Li, and G. Li, "Research Progress of Inorganic Sodium Ion Conductors for Solid-State Batteries," *Chinese Chemical Letters* 36, no. 6 (2025): 110006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccl.2024.110006>.
272. Y. Li, J.-T. Han, C.-A. Wang, H. Xie, and J. B. Goodenough, "Optimizing Li⁺ Conductivity in a Garnet Framework," *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 22, no. 30 (2012): 15357–15361, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2JM31413D>.
273. J. Zhou, M. L. Holekevi Chandrappa, S. Tan, et al., "Healable and Conductive Sulfur Iodide for Solid-State Li-S Batteries," *Nature* 627, no. 8003 (2024): 301–305, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07101-z>.
274. S. Wang, Q. Bai, A. M. Nolan, et al., "Lithium Chlorides and Bromides as Promising Solid-State Chemistries for Fast Ion Conductors With Good Electrochemical Stability," *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 58, no. 24 (2019): 8039–8043, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201901938>.

275. K. Wang, Q. Ren, Z. Gu, et al., "A Cost-Effective and Humidity-Tolerant Chloride Solid Electrolyte for Lithium Batteries," *Nature Communications* 12, no. 1 (2021): 4410, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24697-2>.
276. S. Li, Z. Yang, S.-B. Wang, et al., "Sulfide-Based Composite Solid Electrolyte Films for All-Solid-State Batteries," *Communications Materials* 5, no. 1 (2024): 44, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43246-024-00482-8>.
277. Z. Yang, B. Tang, D. Ren, et al., "Advancing Solid-State Sodium Batteries: Status Quo of Sulfide-Based Solid Electrolytes," *Materials Today* 80 (2024): 429–449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2024.08.011>.
278. J. Li, Y. Li, J. Cheng, et al., "A Graphene Oxide Coated Sulfide-Based Solid Electrolyte for Dendrite-Free Lithium Metal Batteries," *Carbon* 177 (2021): 52–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2021.01.159>.
279. Z. Ren, J. Li, Y. Gong, et al., "Insight into the Integration Way of Ceramic solid-state Electrolyte Fillers in the Composite Electrolyte for High Performance Solid-State Lithium Metal Battery," *Energy Storage Materials* 51 (2022): 130–138, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2022.06.037>.
280. J. Li, F. Xie, W. Pang, Q. Liang, X. Yang, and L. Zhang, "Regulate Transportation of Ions and Polysulfides in All-Solid-State Li-S Batteries Using Ordered-MOF Composite Solid Electrolyte," *Science Advances* 10, no. 11 (2024): ead13925, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.ad13925>.
281. J.-Y. Liang, X.-X. Zeng, X.-D. Zhang, et al., "Engineering Janus Interfaces of Ceramic Electrolyte via Distinct Functional Polymers for Stable High-Voltage Li-Metal Batteries," *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 141, no. 23 (2019): 9165–9169, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.9b03517>.
282. X. Zheng, T. Yang, J. Wei, C. Wang, and M. Chen, "Co-Contribution of Quenching and Nanocrystallization on Ionic-Conductivity Improvement of a Composite Electrolyte of Polyethylene Oxide/Li₇La₃Zr₂O₁₂ Nanofibers at 45°C for All-Solid-State Li Metal Batteries," *Journal of Power Sources* 496 (2021): 229843, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.229843>.